

DELIVERABLE 3.1

REPORT ON THE CO-DESIGN OF CITY-REGIONAL INTEGRATED FOOD STRATEGIES

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HISTORY OF CHANGE

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Number	Page	Change
1	33	Success indicators have been included in 'Table 4: Overview of results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process' in Barcelona
2	14, 23, 35, 46, 57, 62, 76, 85	Phrase "Vision for [name of the city-region]'s future food system" included to make it easier to find the vision statements of consensus reached in each city-region.
4	41	Sentence added: The City of Berlin has adopted a municipal Food Strategy as an ongoing participatory process in collaboration with the Berlin Food Policy Council, a civil society network, starting in 2018.

GLOSSARY

City Regional Food System (CRFS) – Within a geographical region which includes the urban centre and surrounding peri-urban and rural hinterland, “all elements and activities that relate to the production, processing, distribution, preparation and consumption of food, as well as its disposal, [including] the environment, people, processes, infrastructure, institutions and the effects of their activities on our society, economy, landscape and climate”¹.

Food Policy Networks – ‘Networks that represent multiple stakeholders and that may be either sanctioned by a government body or exist independently of government, and address food-related issues and needs within a city, county, state, tribal, multi-county or other designated region’.²

Living Lab (LL) – ‘User-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approaches, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings’ [that] “operate as intermediaries among citizens, research organizations, companies, cities and regions for joint value co-creation, rapid prototyping or validation to scale up innovation”, which includes learning and knowledge production. In FoodCLIC each city-region’s Living Lab comprises one core research partner organization and one practice partner organization.

Real life interventions - Actions implemented by FoodCLIC that aim to produce changes in food environments. These actions may involve either first-time trials of a particular intervention in a city-region or the scaling-out of an on-going initiative at one location in the city-region to other locations in the city-region. The real-life interventions that FoodCLIC is seeking to implement, and scale will allow city-regions to fill gaps in their knowledge and build the evidence-base for policy-making and food-sensitive planning to realize food system transformation.

Food deprived and vulnerable groups - People whose diets are lacking in quantity or nutritional quality (resulting in food safety risks and undernutrition) on account of limited access because of spatiality (e.g., living in ‘food deserts’), living on low income and/or personal circumstances (e.g., institutionalized persons).

¹ EC FOOD 2030 Expert Group (2018) *Recipe for Change: An Agenda for a Climate-Smart and Sustainable Food System for a Healthy Europe*. Brussels: EC, Directorate General for R&I

² Santo, R., Misiaszek, C., Bassarab, K., Harris, D., & Palmer, A. (2021). *Pivoting policy, programs, and partnerships: Food Policy councils’ responses to the crises of 2020*. Johns Hopkins, Center for a livable future. Retrieved from https://assets.jhsph.edu/clf/mod_clfResource/doc/FPC%202020%20Census%20Report_updated.pdf.

1. INTRODUCTION

Europe's urban areas face significant challenges to ensure the availability and consumption of healthy, affordable, safe and sustainably produced food. Such challenges converge within local food environments, but are often neglected by public planners. Promising initiatives taken by municipalities to change the architecture of food choice often fail to become embedded in the wider policy context and to reach deprived and vulnerable groups. Key factors responsible for this are: (1) siloed ways of working and (2) fragmentation of knowledge on facilitators and barriers related to food system transformation. These factors hinder the development and implementation of integrated urban food policies. **The FOODCLIC project aims to create strong science-policy-practice interfaces across eight European city-regions**, which together comprise 45 towns and cities. The backbone of such interfaces are provided by **Food Policy Networks (FPNs)**, which manage real-world experimental **Living Labs (LLs)** to build a policy-relevant evidence-base through learning-in-action. In each of the eight city-regions, an academic partner and a practice partner form a LL team.

Activities in the LLs are informed by an innovative **conceptual framework (the CLIC)**, which emphasizes four desired outcomes of food system integration (sustainability co-benefits, spatial linkages, social inclusion and sectoral connectivities). Capacity-building and direct support for intensive multi-stakeholder engagement (including deprived and vulnerable groups) enable policy actors and urban planners across partner city-regions to develop continuously evolving integrated urban food policies and render planning frameworks food-sensitive. Results are communicated and disseminated amongst others by extending the novel policy practices to another eight city-regions in Europe and Africa, an online Knowledge-Hub, a high-level Think Tank and partners' networks. In these ways, FOODCLIC aims to contribute to **urban food environments that make healthy and sustainable food available, affordable and attractive to all citizens** (including deprived and vulnerable groups).

This report presents the results of **Task 3.2: System understanding, visioning and co-design of integrated city-regional food strategies**. The activities described in this report build on an extensive analysis of each city-region's food systems and the challenges they face. The LL teams also identified gaps in the provision of affordable, sustainable and healthy food for all. Based on the results of this mapping and gapping, the LL teams had organized **collaborative activities to identify key problems** that are responsible for unhealthy urban food environments through joint sense-making (also involving policy-makers, urban planners, city ecologists, designers, researchers). Based on these joint sense-making activities, a **multi-actor visioning workshop** was organized in each LL to create a **shared vision** for the city-regional food system (exploring "where are we now and where do we want to go"), involving various creative techniques as well as deliberation methods to deal with areas of conflict.

A **second workshop on strategic planning** (“and how may we get there”) aimed to create an **integrated city-regional food strategy** for each of the eight city-regions. The results of these workshops are summarized in this report.

To maximize the coherence and compatibility of the approach across the eight city-regions, the project coordination and work package (WP) leadership provided guidance documents, feedback and training sessions to all LL teams. Within this framework, LL teams developed their own place-based strategies to adopt to the case-specific needs and circumstance and to harness upcoming opportunities.

The reports for each case have been written by the respective LL teams and edited by the WP leaders. They follow a shared protocol which was developed by the WP leaders and refined through iterative discussions with all LL teams. For each of the eight city-regions, we first consider the key dynamics of each city-region food system (CRFS) and FPN that were feeding into the visioning and strategy process. We summarize which joint-sensemaking activities took place before the workshops and how these activities helped provide a setting for further system understanding, visioning and strategic planning. This is followed by the description of the first workshop, which aimed to create a shared system understanding and vision (Visioning Workshop). We briefly explain the scene setting and planning, the participants, any special experiences and observations, and finally the visioning results. After that, we describe the setting, observations and results of the Strategic Planning Workshops. The main results of the workshops are summarized in a table for each city-region. Each chapter closes with a reflection by the respective LL team on lessons learned.

Based on the results presented in this report, the strategic plans will be implemented and further refined through an iterative process of reflexive action and learning cycles. Guided by the LL team, the FPNs in each case study city-region will **co-design and implement portfolios of real-life interventions**. Based inter alia on the results presented here, local stakeholders will be invited to co-design real-life interventions in local food environments and interrelated supply chains based on the CLIC framework. **Co-design workshops** will be organized with the active involvement of citizens (including deprived and vulnerable groups), local entrepreneurs (retail, hospitality, start-ups), designers, policy-makers and scientists. **City-walks**, where local inhabitants will show the strengths and weaknesses of their food environments to entrepreneurs, policy-makers, designers, and scientists, will be part of the design process. This will result in **eight plans** with portfolios of real-life interventions, including objectives, activities, responsibility and monitoring and evaluation framework. These plans will be presented in FoodCLIC Deliverable D3.2.

2. LIVING LAB WORKSHOP RESULTS

AARHUS

Photo: Geraldine Vasquez, AU

Context for visioning and strategy workshops

The Aarhus City Council has adopted a Climate Action Plan (2021-2024) that supports the overall green transition in the Aarhus city-region. In addition, Aarhus City Council has also implemented a so-called Climate Political Food Strategy. This strategy contains three goals until 2025: 1) a 25% reduction of the CO₂ footprint of purchased food, 2) less food waste and 3) more climate-friendly food in procurement contracts. Overall, the different plans and strategies related to food contemplate an increase in climate-friendly/plant-based meals in municipal procurement contracts. Moreover, in the context of the Climate Action Plan, it calls for reducing the CO₂ emissions linked to the different aspects of food, from production to distribution. Furthermore, the process regarding the national CO₂ tax will potentially change the dynamics of the food system in major ways. While this was still in the process at the time of the visioning and strategizing activities, it was anticipated to add a substantial influence on the outcomes.

Lastly, there is a general agreement on the need to understand food from a holistic perspective, involving health, social and cultural aspects. Additionally, there is a consensus on the need to continue to direct the food system to a more climate-friendly and sustainable pattern, prioritizing organic and plant-based products. To achieve this, two approaches have been pointed out by the actors: 1) increase the awareness among industry and consumers through education and improvement of food literacy; 2) create or strengthen connections between government (municipality), academia and business to align practices at different levels.

Key challenges: Initially, food was not a major part of the Climate Action Plan (2021-2024) of Aarhus Municipality, but important efforts were made to include this topic to a much larger extent in its revision (currently ongoing). Further, the food system is dominated by big retailers, whereas it is distant from small farmers, thereby increasing the distance between producers and consumers. Regarding interactions and collaboration, the capacities of the different groups tend to be fragmented. In this case, improved collaboration and communication between parties is needed, which could foster new interactions and enrich the food system. During the mapping and gapping activities in the first part of the FoodCLIC project, the Aarhus Living Lab had identified at least 70 actors in the Aarhus food landscape, mainly dominated by the industry and business sectors. In this respect, stakeholders currently are more limited in terms of the important set of connections and capacities that require civil society, perpetuating the current patterns.

In this context, a defined food policy network (FPN) has not yet been established. An officiated FPN could act as a participatory communication platform representing different interests and a forum where needs of variable (and smaller) actors are heard and replied upon through actions and initiatives. Such a platform could provide a common direction along with the necessary independent push towards a more sustainable, fair, transparent and resilient local food system. Establishing an FPN could create a more open and fertile environment for collaboration, enabling interconnections between different actors and thereby creating opportunities to include smaller businesses in the Aarhus food system scene.

Sense-making activities

To provide a basis of joint sense-making prior to the Visioning & Strategy workshops, the Aarhus Living Lab members participated in and hosted several formal and informal exchange events with different actors across the food system. These represented important opportunities to not only facilitate connections between initiatives, but also to build a foundation to take on the challenge of creating a shared understanding of problems and direction of change. It was observed during the process that various organizations had different perspectives and preferred different approaches.

Table 1. Summary of the sense-making activities with participation of the Aarhus Living Lab (hosting or attendee).

DATE	ACTIVITY	TARGET GROUP
Ongoing	Internal network Internal network for colleagues across the municipality who work with green food. The focus is on exchanging experiences, creating synergies and common direction in the food sector in the municipality.	Internal for colleagues in the municipality
Ongoing	Seminar about food (the common good) Participation in a series of seminars about the future of food to gain input and knowledge.	Citizens
25.04.23 (5,5 hours)	Workshop in collaboration with Coop: The future food system is a shared responsibility 40 representatives from across the food system (farmers, small and large food producers, representatives from food service, retail, trade and food organizations) were gathered to discuss what is required of each of us and together to lift a common agenda, where the food system is the focal point.	Business, organizations, education and academia, farmers
15.05.23	FoodCLIC mapping event Workshop for approximately 20 stakeholders across the food system to map the interaction and dynamics between the various food actors in Aarhus and at the same time identify synergies and power dynamics.	Business, organizations, education and academia, farmers
12.08.23	Mariendal (Farmer) Festival Presentation of the FoodCLIC project to the festival's guests and subsequent dialogue about the food system in Aarhus.	Business, organizations, education and academia, farmers
1-3 .09.23	Workshop at Food Festival: The green plate of the future 3 sessions targeted kitchen professionals in the municipality and citizens visiting the festival to collect inputs about their dreams and thoughts for the green plate of the future.	Citizens
12.09.23 (6 hours)	Workshop at the Food, Trends & Sustainability Conference The workshop targeted professionals from the food business sector to collect their input about their dreams and thoughts for a more sustainable food system in the future.	Professionals from the food business sector
26.10.23	Seminar: The Future Food System Presentation by the think tank Frej about the future food system. Followed by a presentation of the EU project FoodCLIC.	Internal for colleagues in the municipality
26.10.23	Workshop: Internal network for green food in Aarhus Municipality Workshop for colleagues working with green food and sustainability. The aim was to identify and discuss actions that can help shape a more sustainable food system in Aarhus Municipality in the future.	Internal for colleagues in the municipality

During this period, the Aarhus Living Lab successfully fostered diverse opportunities to disseminate and increase the project's visibility to different stakeholders, establishing new

connections or enriching already existing ones. More importantly, the key position of the Living Lab has allowed the creation of synergies between the current political context where the Climate Plan is being revised, and the FoodCLIC goals and activities, opening up the discussion about food in this framework and successfully including food as part of the Plan.

Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops – Implementation & Outcomes

Implementation: Aarhus Living Lab conducted two visioning workshops, one on 24th October 2023 in a rented facility and another on 26th October 2023 at the municipality’s rooftop meeting room, both venues situated in vulnerable neighbourhoods. A total of 27 attendees were present between the two visioning events, from over 80 invited participants. The first workshop included representatives from business and academia, policy-makers and the indirect representation of food-deprived groups from the area. The second workshop was mainly arranged by the Living Lab coordinators in Aarhus, with inputs from the Living Lab researchers. It brought together participants of different departments within the Aarhus Municipality, covering consultants, project managers as well as canteen and kitchen workers. Participants were selected as members of an existing network of people in the municipality working on food and sustainability. As it was time for the network to meet again, it made sense to invite them to participate in a visioning workshop to collect their input and perspectives. The invitation was sent by e-mail to everyone in the network with an encouragement to share the invitation with other relevant colleagues in the municipality.

During the visioning process, results and information on the key concepts were shared, including about food environments and the CLIC framework. Participants were then guided through small group work to share their visions of the future food system on illustrations representing Aarhus at different scales i.e., regional, county and neighbourhood level. Exchange between the diverse food system actors made it possible to develop holistic and comprehensive visions. To investigate whether there was consensus and/or divergence in these visions, a voting system was used via

Dotmocracy to categorize whether visions in the maps were achievable/energizing (green), necessary/vital (red), or areas of divergence (yellow).

Table 2: Participating organizations in the visioning workshop (2 events) and the strategic planning workshop (1 event) in Aarhus

VISIONING WORKSHOPS		STRATEGIZING WORKSHOP	
Organisation	Sector	Organisation	Sector
Aarhus Municipality, Mayors department	Government (3)	AB Catering Aarhus A/S (foodservice)	Business/ industry (2)
Aarhus Municipality, Department of Technical Services & Environment	Government (5)	Business With Impact (consultancy)	Business/ industry (1)
Aarhus Municipality, Department of Children & Young People	Government (3)	Dansk Cater (foodservice)	Business/ industry (1)
Aarhus Municipality, Department of Culture & Citizens' Services	Government (2)	Erhvervshus Midtjylland (Business Hub)	Business/industry (1)
Aarhus Municipality, Department of Social Affairs & Employment	Government (2)	Gasa Nord Grønt (supplier of fruit and vegetables)	Business/industry (2)
Aarhus Municipality, Department of Health and Care	Government (4)	Innovation Centre for Organic Farming	Business/industry (2)
Aarhus University	Research/education	Klima Kvikly (retail)	Business/industry (1)
Skraldecafeen (food waste and social organisation)	Civil society (1)	Kontekst Kommunikation (Consultancy)	Business/industry (1)
Tænketanken Frej (Green think tank)	Business/industry (1)	PlanetDairy (start up)	Business/industry (1)
Food and Bio Cluster (business network)	Business/industry (1)	Scandic Aarhus City (hotel)	Business/industry (1)
Agro Food Park	Business/industry (1)	Velas (agricultural advisory company)	Business/industry (2)
Happy Food Forrest (farming)	Civil society (1)	ØKOlageret (supplier of organic fruit and vegetables)	Business/industry (1)
Erhvervshus Midtjylland (Business Hub)	Business/industry (1)	Consultancy	Business/industry (1)
		SEGES Future Farming	Business/industry (1)
		CONCITO (Denmark's green think tank)	Civil society (1)
		Constructive Institutte AU (journalism)	Civil society (1)
		Det Fælles Bedste (NGO)	Civil society (2)
		Happy Food Forest (farming)	Civil society (1)
		Tandergaard (farming)	Civil society (1)
		Skraldecafeen (food waste and social organisation)	Civil society (2)

VISIONING WORKSHOPS		STRATEGIZING WORKSHOP	
Organisation	Sector	Organisation	Sector
		Marienlyst (farming)	Civil society (1)
		Aarhus Kommune (municipality)	Government (10)
		Norddjurs Kommune (municipality)	Government (1)
		Skanderborg Kommune (municipality)	Government (1)
		Politician	Government (1)
		Erhvervs Akademi Århus (Business Academy)	Research/education (2)
		VIA University College	Research/education (1)
		Aarhus University	Research/education (4)
		Aarhus Tech (education)	Research/education (1)

Key understandings of food system problems: Key understandings of major problems in the city-region food system (CRFS), as assessed by the participants during the first workshop, went in several different directions, and largely addressed education, business and industry, and community/system transformation. Many visions revolved around creating more options for growing, harvesting, cooking, and eating locally, in community settings, potentially promoting inclusion in the community, for example through cultural exchange, sharing of experiences, resource sharing, and social interaction in the neighbourhoods – also creating co-benefits between the apparent environmental benefits and social aspects that are addressed.

The second visioning workshop aimed to gather inputs and perspectives on the participants' visions for the future food system in the municipality of Aarhus. As all participants were from the municipality, they had a shared understanding of the CRFS. However, their inputs covered different perspectives and target groups, corresponding to the different departments. To create an initial common understanding, a general introduction to the FoodCLIC project was presented and afterwards, the visioning exercise was explained. The participants were divided between 3 tables. Each table was provided a map of the municipality/city-region.

Vision for Aarhus' future food system: In general terms, there was consensus on how the future food system in Aarhus should look like. The need for food literacy and awareness about the origin of food, and more plant-based diets were recurrent outcomes in the two workshops. In this case, and rooted in the Danish mindset, the outputs were often generally shared and accepted by the attendees (see Supplementary Material 2: Table of consensus and divergence visions).

Strategic planning: The strategizing workshop took place on 30th November 2023 in connection with Aarhus Municipality's yearly climate conference in a conference centre in the city centre of

Aarhus. In connection with the event, it was possible to attend a separate 2-hour workshop focusing on the food system. Hosting the workshop within a larger event was very valuable to attract participants (resulting in a total number of approximately 50 attendees) and to widen the network to a more diverse group.

The theme of the workshop was: “The sustainable food system of the future: From global perspective to local actions”. To create an initial common understanding, the think tank CONCITO³, a pro-climate organization that promotes a green transition by turning knowledge into global action for a climate-neutral society, gave a presentation on the food system and why it needs to change. Afterwards, the workshop was introduced, including a short presentation on FoodCLIC and the CLIC framework. The purpose of the workshop was to discuss possibilities and barriers along four pre-selected themes. The workshop was documented by a facilitator who made a graphical summary (see Figure 1) of each of the four themes as well as a summary of the introductory talk.

The themes were chosen based on the inputs and discussions of the two previous visioning workshops:

- Common direction for the food system
- Food literacy for all
- The plant-based plate of the future
- Where does the food come from?

Figure 1 Graphical summary of strategic discussion on food literacy, one of four key themes in Aarhus

³ For more information visit: <https://concito.dk/en>

While perspectives and priorities differed during the strategic workshop, there was common agreement on the overall vision and direction of the food system in Aarhus towards a more sustainable and plant-based diet; in this direction, potential interventions and measures were identified around the promotion of plant-based food and food literacy, especially among children. Furthermore, there was a strong focus on supporting new innovative business models among (young/new) farmers to enhance the plant-based development and value chain.

Finally, the need for supporting community building around food was addressed as a potential line of action, including the establishment of a Food Policy Network as a point of departure with a focus on public procurement.

Anticipated challenges to realization: The workshops showed a great willingness to find common ground and formulate a shared vision. However, the real-life impact of this willingness still needs to materialise. The most feasible interventions will revolve around facilitative education opportunities and hubs for learning and knowledge sharing. However, for long-term and wider impact, political support needs to be created, requiring a continuous effort and the mobilization of resources, including different departments within the municipality. Regarding possible barriers to achieve the completion of the interventions, it is a potential risk that actors and partners involved (teachers, canteen managers, or farmers) can drop their participation at any time. This means that constant engagement with these actors is needed to carry out the activities.

Table 3: Overview of results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process in Aarhus

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Food literacy	Increase the theoretical and practical knowledge of food	Development and deployment of information/communication campaigns	Support from nutritional, safety and culinary experts. Responsible: households	Nutritional (national) recommendations; Knowledge on how to cook and safely preserve foods (e.g. pulses); Increase in home-made food
Origin of food	Theoretical and practical knowledge on the origin of food. Where does the food come from?	Create a school activity for students to get closer to food	Farmers that can support with hands-on experiences. Responsible: school staff	Integration of the proposed activities as part of the annual school plan

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Plant-based meals	Increase the consumption of plant-based meals	Apply and integrate the Danish national dietary guidelines in publicly and privately procured food, for example canteens in workplaces or universities	Responsible: canteen management, procurement officers	Tackle of: - Hedonic aspects ("tasty"); - Preparation/cooking aspects ("easy"); - Eating culture (main meal = meat)
Common direction of the food system	Companies, citizens, and public authorities are working together on a more plant-based food system	Establish an FPN that can support future discussions and changes in the food system	Recruitment of people from different groups. Legal guidance on how to formally establish the FPN. Responsible: members of the FPN, legal advisors	Participation and representation of different groups. Common vision on the food system. Continuation after the FoodCLIC project.
Locally produced food	Boost and promote short supply chains and support local farmers in the development of a business model	Elaborate a business model for local farmers in a highly competitive environment	Recruitment of farmers and business advisors to develop a business plan, considering the characteristics of the local market. Responsible: local farmers	The establishment of a successful and sustainable business model (farmers market, subscription for box delivery, collect-yourself, etc) that survives beyond the duration of the FoodCLIC project

Lessons learned in Aarhus through the visioning & strategic planning process

Throughout the workshop experience, summoning and supporting a stakeholder network was challenging, especially regarding the vulnerable target groups (farmers) and representatives of big retailers. A possible explanation refers to the heavily theoretical aspect of the initial phases of the project, the lack of concrete impact in the short term and the natural fatigue that comes with repeated participation in the workshops. Agricultural workers and business owners have particularly high logistical barriers and costs to participation and would require more investigation on strategies for successful engagement.

In general, participants found it interesting to take part in visioning and strategic planning, especially with the opportunity for networking. However, there is a need recognized by participants to capture more unconventional ideas and bring them into the discussions – often there was consensus and an unanticipated level of agreement, which might have been also reinforced by the Danish communication culture, but it could also be due to the lack of direct representation from retailers and vulnerable groups who might have articulated other ideas and interests. Finally, there was a notable tendency to focus on practicalities, e.g. assessing whether a vision was possible.

AMSTERDAM

Photo: LFeenstra

Context for visioning and strategy workshops

The Amsterdam Metropolitan Area (AMA) region contains 30 municipalities across two provinces, and is characterised by a patchwork of food-related policies. The provincial governments of both North Holland and Flevoland have created a food vision in recent years. In addition, the municipalities of Almere and Amsterdam have improved and amended their food strategies during the first year of the FoodCLIC project (2022-2023). Several other municipalities have expressed interest in drafting a food strategy, such as Haarlem, Purmerend, Haarlemmermeer and Gooise Meren. These policy and government actors collaborate with Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) and Research Organisation (ROs), as well as with stakeholders from business and industry in the food policy network 'Voedsel Verbindt'. The Metropolitan Area contains several other food-related networks, namely Food Council MRA, based in Amsterdam and Haarlem Food Future, an FPN in Haarlem. Both networks engage with governments as representatives of citizens and citizen-led initiatives. For FoodCLIC, the Living Lab team has focused on engaging more citizen-led initiatives, some broader business and industry partners, as well as a diverse group of policy-makers.

Considering the complex food policy landscape, there are three main challenges related to the implementation of integrated food policy:

- 1) The view that food is not a political priority, is dominant, and food-related policy domains remain highly disconnected. In several cases, municipal real estate departments and city planners are not involved in food policy.
- 2) The inclusion of diverse stakeholders, especially citizens, proves to be challenging for networks and governments alike. Citizens do not manage to access government-mediated resources, while governments fail to find connection with inspiring initiatives that can serve as best practices. The FoodCLIC Living Lab team has focused primarily on improving this situation, with an alignment of priorities and close collaboration on this issue with the municipality of Amsterdam. However, other cities and rural regions in the AMA are less well represented. There is an unjustifiably large geographical bias in the region, gravitating towards Amsterdam-based citizens and initiatives.
- 3) The disconnect between different government levels complicates action on a regional basis. The provincial and municipal governments not only have differences in terms of scale but also operate in different policy arenas.

Sense-Semaking activities

Four different joint sense-making sessions were organized in order to help validate key results from the mapping and gapping of food environments, stakeholder networks and the AMA policy landscape during the earlier phase of the FoodCLIC project. The first session was held during a bi-monthly meeting of the informal food initiatives network in Amsterdam Noord, one of the two city-districts selected as target areas for the project – this was a continuation of the dialog and presence of the Living Lab at these regular meetings since March 2023. Approximately 30 attendees joined the meeting to review preliminary mapping and gapping results, take part in a follow-up mapping activity and facilitate a tour and a workshop on edible oils. The goal was to inform and collect feedback, but also to have fun together and to give back to the people who had

taken the time to participate in mapping and gapping over the past few months. People generally recognized themselves in the findings presented and shared some additional insights. Some organizations voiced concerns on topics including trust between government and residents, the temporary nature of places and funding, and not feeling adequately valued for their efforts in helping communities.

This community event was followed by an interactive presentation of results during the steering committee of Voedsel Verbindt, the FPN in the city-region and practice partner in the Living Lab. The steering committee provided positive feedback and encouraged expanding the focus of activities beyond Amsterdam and the consumer perspective. The Living Lab team also met with the representative for the food transition in the Gooise Meren municipality to validate results with an organization that had not participated in the mapping and gapping activities, and to solicit further insights from the experience of those engaging closely with farmers and nature organisations. Finally, a living lab joint sense-making session helped pulling together the common agenda for the visioning workshop and to communicate results to stakeholders.

Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops – Implementation & Outcomes

Implementation: The AMA FoodCLIC Visioning workshop was organized over a full day on the 10th November 2023 in a neighbourhood centre in Amsterdam Zuidoost, one of the city-districts of Amsterdam that were more closely investigated during the mapping and gapping phase of FoodCLIC. The workshop programme included 3 facilitated workshops, 4 food tours of different food environments in the neighbourhood, and 2 presentations on the concept of food environments and the mapping and gapping results. In total, 65 participants from across sectors and organizations attended the visioning event (see Table below). Invitations were sent to the Voedsel Verbindt network and those engaged in the mapping and gapping activities in the first part of the FoodCLIC project, and these groups were welcome to extend the workshop invitation to other stakeholders they felt were relevant. With this strategy, the aim was to ensure a strong variety in representation from neighbourhoods, city level and city-regional level and across sectors. The workshop was promoted through email for all official partners and entities. With more informal networks, we used WhatsApp groups to spread the word, as well as LinkedIn and the Amsterdam Smart City platform. Despite active recruitment of representatives of the Amsterdam Zuidoost city-district where the event was held, a full-day workshop turned out as a barrier to participation.

leaving most representation from initiatives in the city-district Noord. A compensation of € 60 was offered for attendees who participated in all three workshops and would have had to miss work during workshop hours in order to value their time or otherwise missed income from work.

Table 4: Participating organizations in the Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops in Amsterdam

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
GroenplatVorm Zuidoost (Neighbourhood platform for Green initiatives)	Civil Society	GroenplatVorm Zuidoost (Neighbourhood platform for Green initiatives)	Civil Society (2)
Breed Informeel Voedsel Overleg (Broad Informal Food Network)	Civil Society	Breed Informeel Voedsel Overleg (Broad Informal Food Network)	Civil Society (2)
Food Council MRA	Civil Society	Food Council MRA	Civil Society (2)
Haarlem Food Future (FPN)	Civil Society	Haarlem Food Future (FPN)	Civil Society (2)
Tuindorp Deli-cious (Food initiative)	Civil Society	Helen's Free Food Market	Civil Society
The None Waste Project	Civil Society	HeelHaarlemmermeer (Food initiative in Municipality Haarlemmermeer)	Civil Society (2)
Kraak en smaak (Food initiative)	Civil Society	Voedselcirkel Amsterdam (food initiative)	Civil Society
Natuur voor Kinderen (Nature for Kids)	Civil Society	Nationale Jeugdraad (national youth council)	Civil Society
Helen's Free Food Market	Civil Society (2)	Green Meal Initiative	Civil Society
HeelHaarlemmermeer (Food initiative in Municipality Haarlemmermeer)	Civil Society	Jonge Sla (food initiative)	Civil Society
Natuurlijk Diemen (Nature initiative in municipality of Diemen)	Civil Society	Moestuinschool Amsterdam (Urban gardening school)	Civil Society
De Gezonde Stad (Amsterdam platform for initiatives)	Civil Society (2)	The Land Amsterdam	Civil Society
City Plot	Civil Society	Municipality of Amsterdam	Government (4)
Beemstergaard CSA	Civil Society	Municipality of Almere	Government
Voedselcirkel Amsterdam (food initiative)	Civil Society (2)	Province of Flevoland	Government (2)
Municipality of Almere	Government	MRA-Bureau	Government
Municipality of Amsterdam	Government (4)	University of Applied Sciences	Research (2)
Province of North Holland	Government	EU4Advice	Research
Province of Flevoland	Government	VU	Research
GGD Amsterdam (Municipal Health Department)	Government	Squarewise	Business (2)
Municipality of Schiedam	Government	Boeren van Amstel	Business
Municipality Purmerend	Government (2)	Verbroederij (restaurant, event center)	Business
AMS Institute	Research (5)		
University of Applied Sciences	Research		

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
EU4Advice (Other EU Project)	Research		
Big Data Value Center	Research		
Amsterdam Green Campus	Research		
Flevo Campus	Research		
Boeren voor Buren (Selling food directly from farmers to food initiatives)	Business		
Amped Concepts	Business		
BeBright (consultancy)	Business		
ECONNECTS	Business (2)		
DieetPlaneet dietitian)	Business		
Restaurant Elixer	Business		
SAIL Amsterdam (biggest event in A'dam)	Business		
Juicity (Juice maker)	Business		
Rabobank	Business		
Baking Lab (bakery)	Business (2)		
Vereniging Flevofood (farmer representative)	Business		
TommyTomato	Business		
De Oesterzwammerij (mushroom farm)	Business		

Visioning: The first workshop focused on creative visioning, with small groups for each specific food environment. Participants were asked to write up and draw their vision for the food environment, considering the CLIC framework and the key question: How important will each food environment be in 2050? During the visioning workshop, 12 key words were identified that embody the overall vision drafted by all participants (figure 2).

Figure 2: Keywords representing the common food system vision

Vision for Amsterdams' future food system: Many stakeholders present during the day envisioned a food environment with certain key aspects and drivers of change in which the community will be

highly involved. Across the board, from supermarkets to school meals, the community had a place. Key drivers included the high value placed on redefining people's relationship with food – through education, urban agriculture and linkages to the role of rural farmers, not only as stewards of food production and the landscape, including pesticide reduction, but also in co-creating knowledge for peri-urban farming. In this vein, access to land was seen as a key driver of change.

Next, participants were given several 'tensions' within the current organisation of the food system, based on the mapping and gapping results, which focused on issues of governance, networks, trust-building and the use of public space. Through several rounds of facilitated discussion and small group interactions, participants responded to these challenges from their own experiences and knowledge of best-practice examples.

Strategic Planning: The strategic planning workshop, conducted on the afternoon of 22nd January 2024 at the AMA office, built upon the foundations established during the visioning session. The strategic planning session, designed to be more concise than the visioning event, attracted 33 stakeholders. These participants, primarily case owners of potential interventions and strategic partners like the provinces of North Holland and Flevoland and the AMA bureau, represented a diverse range of interests, ensuring an equitable distribution of power among the envisioned neighbourhood-oriented and food grower-oriented interventions. The attendees included six business representatives, primarily from food production and small-scale consultancy sectors, nine governmental officials from both the municipal and the provincial level, sixteen public stakeholders representing neighbourhood-based food initiatives, and two researchers specializing in community-service learning practices. The methodology was participatory and dynamic, including a) exploration of each intervention pathway divided into three rounds, enabling participants to engage deeply with each possibility, and b) informed decision-making, as stakeholders were encouraged to 'score' each pathway based on comprehensive discussions.

The strategic planning workshop resulted in five strategic pathways to explore during the ensuing co-design process (see Figure 3). Three of them are core pathways for interventions.

Figure 3: Representation of the pathways developed during the workshops in Amsterdam

- The first pathway centres on neighbourhood-based interventions in three areas: Haarlem Schalkwijk, Amsterdam Noord and Amsterdam Zuidoost. In Amsterdam, the collaboration between different societal stakeholders on the topic of food is the key starting point for interventions. In Haarlem, the exploration and execution of cooperative food initiatives is pursued together with the network Haarlem Food Future and key partners.
- The second pathway (institutional) explores the potential of public procurement as a tool for food system transformation. Here, large employers in the AMA have expressed interest to join a community of practice (CoP) that should facilitate learning on alternative ways of procuring, for example through short food supply chains (SFSC) and community wealth building (CWB). Several organisations that aim to transform their catering by 2026 will join the CoP.
- A third pathway focuses on the element of 'space'. In the Netherlands, land availability and land prices are key drivers in food system transformation. In this strategic pathway, stakeholders explore how cooperatives can facilitate access to land in order to strengthen urban-rural linkages and to increase income security for farmers.

- The fourth and fifth pathway revolve around the creation of a learning ecosystem in the city-region and a policy trajectory. The latter aims to involve policy-makers from different municipalities in putting food on the agenda by creating municipality-specific food strategies.

Anticipated challenges to realization: Some of the core elements of the strategy, such as the timeline, resource allocation and (shared) responsibilities have not been discussed in detail during the workshop, due to a lack of time. Several policy-makers emphasized the need to match the FoodCLIC strategy to current policy goals and programmes. Simultaneously, attendants stressed the need for (transformative) action, as opposed to just ‘pushing paper’. This split could indicate a potential barrier to collaboration in the strategy. Towards the end of the (half-day) session, the participants mandated the Living Lab team to work out a plan in the form of a strategic document in which the above-mentioned gaps can be addressed.

On a conceptual level, attendants found it difficult to identify strategic pathways and actions that would directly contribute to the realisation of co-benefits. Instead, many participants struggled to circumvent a ‘capitalist’ mindset in the current food system, articulating that economic gains were incompatible with social and environmental sustainability goals. Other key concepts that emerged as important during the discussion were the urban-rural linkages and inclusion in the form of food sovereignty, and the important although undecided role of supermarkets and large corporations in the future of food provisioning. Probably more unrealistic were calls for the government to intervene in the food environment. While the group gathered for the event was in favour of more food environment-related policy, nationally such interventions are unlikely to be adopted.

Table 5: Overview or results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process in Amsterdam

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Food and nutrition	Creating more healthy food environments	Creating access to neighbourhood gardens	Number of citizens accessing urban gardens
		Preventive health programmes in neighbourhoods	Meet daily recommended intake of fresh fruits and vegetables
	Making healthy choices the norm	Improve food literacy of neighbourhood cooks	
Sustainability	Creating more sustainable food environments	Stimulate organic practices in urban gardens	No. of urban gardens working according to organic standards No. of CSAs working based on organic practices
		Local production of vegetables	Regional production of vegetables Land use share for fruit/vegetable production
	Closing nutrient cycles in the city-regional food system	Composting initiatives within neighbourhoods for urban gardening	No. of people composting food Gardener’s opinion on compost quality

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
		Composting initiative with hospitality sector	Farmer's accessing compost in AMA
	Protein transition	Stimulate protein transition in institutional food environments	Amount of protein stemming from plant/animal sources
Space	Making healthy and sustainable food <i>accessible</i> to all		
	Strengthening <i>urban-rural linkages</i> .		No. of AMA/neighbourhood citizens involved in food growing
	Create food sensitive neighbourhoods that centre on health and sustainability	Increase food sensitivity of urban planning	Urban planning with specific attention for food environments % of land dedicated to food production in neighbourhoods
	Localizing food systems	Stimulate consumption of local production	% of food produced locally that is consumed locally
Economics & governance	Making food affordable for all	Start community restaurants with affordable meals	No. of plates served in community restaurants
	Securing fair prices and wages for everyone involved in the food economy	Making use of cooperative models where producers can set their own price.	
	Creating common space for food in cities		Increase in no. of city-farms.
	Creating common space for food production in rural areas	Facilitate collaboration between farms and citizen initiatives	No. and % of farms collaborating with citizen initiatives
	Stimulating community initiatives that aim to change food environments		

Lessons learned in Amsterdam through the visioning & strategic planning process

Overall, key lessons related to organisation, balancing science and practice, and stakeholder engagement.

With regard to **organisation**, we observed that conversations became dominated by unexpected topics. Sometimes this could be explained with the absence of key stakeholders. However, even with all the stakeholders present, we often did not manage to make the anticipated progress. Different stakeholders did not always make the contributions that we expected. Nevertheless, we were also surprised by the enthusiasm of different attendants to contribute to the different topics at the table, regardless of whether these topics directly affected them. Participants reported that

although it was overwhelming to see the complexity of the issues related to the food system, they felt that the workshops had broadened their perspective on the challenges that different stakeholders perceive and experience as well as the importance of networks.

In terms of **balancing science and practice**, we noticed that co-creative workshops as part of a 'scientific' project require a careful shaping of the events. This is illustrated by the fact that our workshops during the visioning session resulted in scattered outcomes and lack of clarity among participants due to the vastness and depth of the topic. The depth created through the mapping and gapping in the earlier stage of the FoodCLIC project sometimes blurred the design trajectory for attendants, as they became overly entangled in the complexities of the topic at hand. During the strategizing workshop, we managed to find a better balance, mainly by organising the workshops in a different way. We shifted our focus to simplified questions and templates and having regular wrap-up moments in between workshop sessions, when table facilitators brought key outcomes of a session back to the group.

Lastly, regarding **stakeholder engagement**, the workshops progressed in bringing together a mixed group of stakeholders that represented both heard and unheard voices in the food system. In many cases, it was difficult to include underrepresented stakeholders, such as farmers and food producers, food-deprived groups, undocumented persons or people who did not speak Dutch. Particularly in the case of farmers and undocumented residents, this probably resulted in less attention for their struggles. While in the case of the larger companies, their absence resulted in the participants making explicit decisions on their behalf. Inviting these groups is only the first step to ensure that their concerns are reflected in the final output. Equitable participation requires attentive facilitation and time investment. Moreover, sharing information and preparing stakeholders to empower them in advance can be helpful to contribute to future activities, for example by strengthening contact to key figures in neighbourhoods such as Amsterdam Zuidoost. Here it is important to mention that in many cases, the vagueness of the planning stage of these workshops made it difficult for stakeholders to prioritize them over urgent matters with more acute and tangible benefits.

BARCELONA

Context for visioning and strategy workshops

With the city of Barcelona as its central hub, the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona (AMB) constitutes a region where the food sector plays a predominant economic role through various operations involving production, distribution, commercialization, and consumption. However, these activities also exert significant social, economic, territorial and environmental pressures.

Simultaneously, the metropolitan region is highly proactive and dynamic in its food policies and initiatives, aiming to transform the food system. Barcelona was Sustainable Food World Capital in 2021 and food strategies have already been developed at regional, metropolitan and municipal scale. This commitment encompasses the administrative domain, the research sector, enterprises in the realm of social economy, and social initiatives from civil society organisations.

At regional scale, various sectoral food networks exist which unite different stakeholders, and there are some cross-sectional coordination spaces, mainly driven by public institutions at metropolitan scale. Nonetheless, these spaces have notably limited capacities to implement effective transformative measures.

Key challenges in this context refer, on the one hand, to the growing importance of the influences on and impacts of the food system in terms of food security, food poverty, access and affordability to healthy and sustainable food, food waste, lack of food literacy or dietary habits to deal with the worrying increase of health problems, worsening conditions in the primary sector, or environmental degradation due to food production and distribution.

On the other hand, food-related problems need to be prioritised on the public agenda to bring more attention to the need to reinforce, organize, balance and align the different stakeholders, resources, strategic plans, policies, and capacities towards a process of shared understanding and

decision-making to increase collective impact. Even if multiple food plans and policies have been deployed in the Metropolitan Area of Barcelona, the main challenge is that public intervention can be enhanced and empowered to reduce the inequalities and unsustainability produced by present tendencies in the food system.

Sense-making activities

The Barcelona Living Lab team has been carrying out preparatory activities at different scales to prepare the workshops and to ensure their smooth operation. On the one hand, **visual tools (maps and videos)** summarizing the results of the diagnosis for each of the selected neighbourhoods were produced to facilitate effective communication with the participants of the workshops while ensuring easy comprehension and synthesis of the main ideas related to the food environment of each neighbourhood. On the other, the Living Lab team members have participated in different **meetings and events** to foster the networking and engagement of food-related stakeholders in the FoodCLIC process, including **presentations** in universities that are working on food system observatories, workshops at municipal scale or meetings with the public district-scale authorities of each of the neighbourhoods, as well as **direct contact** with relevant stakeholders to share detailed feedback and explore the need to get engaged in FoodCLIC. During these meetings, the FoodCLIC framework and the key messages of the project were generally well received and greeted as a complementary and necessary approach to improve the current situation of the CRFS and to enhance the value of the interventions that the different stakeholders are undertaking to improve their impact at all scales.

Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops – Implementation & Outcomes

Implementation: The Living Lab team in Barcelona considered that conducting a single workshop on visioning or strategizing would not effectively engage local stakeholders from the grassroots scale or establish the conditions to assure equal opportunities to participate without power inequalities. Therefore, workshops were organised either at **neighbourhood scale** with both morning and afternoon options, and at **metropolitan scale** with actors from the CRFS of the AMB. In the neighbourhoods, **separated workshops** were also organized with **citizens and professionals** for the same reasons. This approach was based on the **System-Oriented Dialogue Model**⁴. This model was adapted for the system understanding and visioning workshops to include the following steps: first, system understanding used neighbourhood maps as tools to validate the main characteristics of each food environment. In this activity, participants edited food environment elements as well as added new ones using sticky notes and writing directly on the maps.

For the visioning process, an adaptation of the Three Horizons framework was used; this is a future-oriented framework that aims at tackling complex problems with uncertain futures (i.e., first horizon asking: where are we right now and why is it this way?; the second horizon: identification of inspiring initiatives; and a third horizon: what future would we like to have?). Using this methodological approach, **a series of 8 face-to-face workshops** was implemented which took place in municipal or social association venues and facilities in the Metropolitan area (Table 1).

⁴ Malagrida, R., Fernández, J., Casabona, J., Broerse, J.E.W. (2023): A System-Oriented Dialogue Model to Design Community Partnerships for More Effective Sars-Cov-2 Prevention in Schools: The Case of Spain, International Journal of Public Health 68, <https://doi.10.3389/ijph.2023.1605624>.

Table 6: Overview of the visioning and strategic planning workshop series in Barcelona

SYSTEM UNDERSTANDING AND VISIONING WORKSHOPS			
Date	Time	Place	Attendees
20/11/23	17.30 to 20	Sant Cosme	8 citizens and professionals from associations in the neighbourhood
23/11/23	11.30 to 14	Sant Cosme	21 professionals from the local administration (7), social organisations (6) and social enterprises (8)
29/11/23	11.30 to 14	Fondo	14 professionals from the local administration (5), health services (4), cultural integration services (2), social enterprises (1) and social organisations (3)
30/11/23	9.30 to 13.30	City region AMB	22 professionals from public administrations (8), research (7), social organisations (4) and social enterprises (3)
10/01/24	10 to 11.30	Fondo	10 participants: citizens from civil society (9) and 1 professional from the public administration

STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOPS			
Date	Time	Place	Attendees
23/01/24	9.15 to 13.30	Fondo	9 participants: public administration (6) social enterprise (1), civil society organisation (1), research sector (1)
26/01/24		Sant Cosme	13 participants: public administration (6), social organisations (3), social enterprises (3) education organisation (1)
31/01/24		City region AMB	23 participants from the administration (5), research (7), social enterprises (6) and civil society (5)

The methodologies used during the system understanding and visioning workshops were aimed at engaging and motivating participants. In particular, the workshop formats were designed with a special focus on sharing knowledge, expertise and experiences to enrich the collective reflections and co-creation processes, and overall led to a positive atmosphere and high level of motivation among participants.

Table 7: Participating organizations in the visioning and strategic planning workshops in Barcelona

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Municipality of Santa Coloma de Gramenet, Health Department	Government (2)	Municipality of Santa Coloma de Gramenet, Health department	Government (2)
Fundació Hospital Esperit Sant (FHES)	Research (2)	Municipality of Santa Coloma de Gramenet, Social Services	Government
Municipality of Santa Coloma de Gramenet, Social Services	Government	ACAU	Civil Society
ICS, CAP Sta Rosa-Can Mariner (Health service)	Government	Municipality of Santa Coloma de Gramenet, Environmental services	Government
CNL L'Heura (catalan education service)	Government (2)	ICS, CAP Sta Rosa – Can Mariner (Health service)	Government

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
ACAU (social integration)	Civil Society	ICS, CAP Riu Nord – Riu Sud (Health service)	Government
Fundació Germina (social integration)	Civil Society (2)	ICS (Health service)	Government
Municipality of Santa Coloma de Gramenet, Environmental services	Government	Municipality of Santa Coloma de Gramenet, Health department	Government
ICS, CAP Fondo (health service)	Government	University of Barcelona	Research
Arran de Terra (cooperative for agroecology)	Private sector	Fundació Germina	Civil Society
Conversatories	Civil Society (5)	La Botiga (social enterprise promoted by the municipality for food security)	Government (2)
Municipality of Santa Coloma de Gramenet, Fondo municipal office	Government (2)	Fundació Espigoladors (non-profit organisation aiming to reduce food waste)	Private sector
Comunalitat Benviure	Civil Society (2)	SPAI (drug addiction municipal service)	Government
Espai GISC (youth informal education)	Civil Society (5)	ICS (health office in Sant Cosme)	Government
Amics Pota Blava (social association in the neighbourhood of Sant Cosme)	Civil Society	Consorci del Parc Agrari del Baix Llobregat (Agrarian park office)	Government
Fundació Rubricatus – social integration	Civil Society (2)	La Casa dels Futurs (civil association for agroecology)	Civil Society
Fundació Espigoladors – prevention of food waste	Private sector	Municipality of El Prat de Llobregat (social economy)	Government
Municipality of El Prat de Llobregat – Sant Cosme municipal office	Government (3)	Espai GISC (youth informal education)	Civil Society (2)
SPAI (drug addiction municipal service)	Government	Municipality of El Prat de Llobregat (education services)	Government
Antenes Comunitaries (social association in the neighbourhood of Sant Cosme)	Civil Society	Municipality of El Prat de Llobregat – Sant Cosme municipal office	Government (2)
Consorci del Parc Agrari del Baix Llobregat (Agrarian park office)	Government	Llar d'infants Dumbo (nursery school in Sant Cosme)	Government
Som Esqueix (coop for communitarian agrarian activities)	Private sector	Alterbanc (Food distribution center)	Private sector
Amics de Sant Cosme (social association in the neighbourhood)	Civil Society (2)	Associació Cultural i Gastronòmica Manjaretti	Civil Society
ATS (social organisation for social empowerment)	Civil Society	AMB (Urban planning)	Government
Municipality of El Prat de Llobregat (coordination services)	Government	Fundesplai (cantines management, education)	Private sector
Municipality of El Prat de Llobregat (social economy)	Government	La Fabric@ (coop for social innovation)	Private sector

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Fundació Secretariat Gitano (Social entity for gypsy citizens)	Civil Society	ITA Salut mental (Mental Health services)	Government
IRTA (Food & agriculture research centre)	Research (2)	Gencat. Agència de Salut Pública de Catalunya (Regional Government Public Health Office)	Government (2)
Municipality of Barcelona	Government (3)	Càritas Barcelona (social aid)	Civil Society
Keras Buti cooperativa agroecològica	Private sector	Universitat Oberta de Catalunya	Research
PEMB (Strategic Plan for Barcelona)	Government	Municipality of Barcelona	Government
Associació Cultural I Gastronòmica Manjaretti	Civil Society	Gencat. Dept Drets Socials (Regional Government Social Rights Office)	Government
AMB (Urban planning)	Government	Conreu Sereny SCCL (farmers coop)	Private sector
Institut Metropolí	Research	Economat Social SCCL (consumers' coop)	Private sector
Càritas Barcelona (social aid)	Civil Society	Associació Vida Sana (Civil association for healthy life)	Civil Society
La Fundició (Coop for communitarian activities)	Private sector	Nutrició sense fronteres (Development ONG)	Civil Society
Universitat Ramon Llull	Research	Collegi de Dietistes – Untricionistes de Catalunya (Nutrition professional association)	Civil Society
Nutrició sense fronteres (Development ONG)	Civil Society	I2CAT	Research
Gencat (Regional gov). Dept for Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda	Government (2)	Keras Buti cooperativa agroecològica	Private sector
CREDA	Research	IDIAP Jordi Gol (Social innovation)	Research
Fundesplai (canteens management, education)	Private sector		
University of Barcelona	Research		
Unió de Pagesos (farmer's trade union)	Civil Society		
Universitat Oberta de Catalunya	Research		
AMB (Economic development)	Government		

Key understandings of food systems problems: The participants perceived that there is a need to establish a FPN to foster collaboration for shared understanding and for developing shared action plans in neighbourhoods with deprived populations that show that a different relationship to food – based on a community-supported and integrated approaches – can be a better option to respond to the constantly evolving challenges in the food system. Starting with small-scale pilot

interventions is a value for experimenting on how to facilitate the transition of the food system. The learning processes will be key to scale up the interventions once they have proven effective.

Vision for Barcelona's future food system: Despite the pressing and urgent need to change the food system, the main barriers perceived to achieve a future positive vision for food system transformation were the dominant economic dynamics, the difficulties in empowering communities, and the need to address inequalities that lead to disadvantaged or vulnerable populations. Even if holding some reluctance among some of the stakeholders, the resulting vision statement agreed was:

"In the year 2050, we will have urban food environments that will facilitate access to healthy, sustainable, local, fair, attractive and affordable food for everyone. This will be achieved through empowering communities, including people in vulnerable situations, and addressing the cultural diversity of food."

Strategic planning: For each of the three strategic planning workshops, the same methodology was followed; the workshops started with exercises where the results from previous workshops were summarised, reviewed and validated, after which each participant was asked to do an individual reflection on how their organisation's aims (could) contribute to the issues identified, with a view to consider the approaches specific to the FoodCLIC project. These reflections were shared with all participants which allowed for a collective visualization of possible connections.

Next, participants were invited to do an initial prioritisation of the themes to be addressed in terms of suitability to address identified food problems in the neighbourhoods, potential impact and feasibility. Participants were then grouped according to these thematic priorities and started to propose possible aims and interventions to be implemented in the neighbourhoods or at regional level. Cards with objectives and ideas of solutions from previous workshops were distributed to support creative thinking within these groups, which brought together participants from different sectors and organisations.

Anticipated challenges to realization: Time is always a limiting factor for the ability to develop an empowered and consistent community process within the FPN. In addition, the Barcelona Living Lab workshops have resulted in several proposals that will need to be prioritized and merged. On the other hand, the necessary adaptation of the implementation of interventions to the legal and economic-administrative management standards of the public administrations that are part of this project could in some way condition the actions that may be developed.

Table 8: Overview of results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process in Barcelona

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
FONDO				
Infrastructure for food communities	Promote community cooking and food self-sufficiency in the neighbourhood	Facilitate free access to public centres when not in service (e.g. school kitchens, universities, Fondo library, social canteens) through collaborative pilots with a network of suppliers, local entities, citizens, etc.	Germina Foundation, Associació Coordinadora d' Ajuda Mútua (ACAU)	Quantity of public centres; Quantity & type of activities; People using them
Participation and networking	Enhance networking among food stakeholders in the neighbourhoods.	Create and consolidate a participatory community structure that among other actions, will consolidate and continuously update a map of neighbourhood assets related to food, and will coordinate the sharing of resources and capacities.	Public health service (Institut Català de la Salut), Public Health City Council, ACI, neighbourhood associations + civic centres, Open Centres, social dining rooms, Heura (Adult School for linguistic normalisation), Fundació Tallers, enterprise for promoting occupation (GramImpuls), all organizations related to food	People/organizations taking part; Mapped neighbourhood ; Coordination systemics; Methodologies for sharing; Degree of use of this resource
Food sovereignty, empowerment and food diversity	Promote diverse and healthy eating, taking into account food diversity and improving the social integration	Create community references to promote diverse food options by organizing workshops in public spaces and schools. Incorporate diversity criteria in neighbourhood cultural activities	City Council, Educational Centres, Primary healthcare services, local Entities, and Associations	Nb of referees; variety in nationalities of referees; workshops organised & attendees
Information, education, and events, advertising, narrative	Improve public information and knowledge through public services	Train professionals and the general population in healthy and sustainable nutrition	Institut Català de la Salut (ICS), Dept of Education, Germina Foundation, University of Barcelona, GramImpuls, Associació Coordinadora d' Ajuda Mútua (ACAU)	Nb and type of professionals trained; Nb of learning activities;

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
SANT COSME				
Local production, processing, and distribution	Improve access to healthy and sustainable products	Open “La Botiga del Prat” to the entire population (not only for deprived groups) and at the same time expand the offering of sustainable products with local, seasonal and agroecological products	Consorci Parc Agrari, City Council, GATS, ABD, Fundació Espigoladors, producers, Comunalitat, consumer groups	Increase of users/ buyers in La Botiga; Increase on the offer /purchase of local and sustainable products
Local production, processing, and distribution	Promote and inspire agroecological production with a cooperative example at Cal Mones	Recover soil for agricultural use and promote a productive project of social and community self-management	Agriculture for the Territory, El Prat city Council, La Casa dels Futurs (NGO), Arran de Terra (food cooperative)	Nº of square metres of soil recovered for agricultural use Nº of people in the community Quantity and type of products
Local production, processing, and distribution	Improve access to healthy and sustainable products	Expand the offering of sustainable products from La Botiga del Prat with local seasonal agroecological products, opening the supermarket to the entire population	Agrarian Park consortium (Consorci Parc Agrari del Baix Llobregat), El Prat de Llobregat City Council, GATS (NGO), ABD (NGO), Fundació Espigoladors, producers, Comunalitat Benviure network, consumer groups	Increase of users/ buyers in La Botiga; Increase on the offer /purchase of local and sustainable products
Information and narratives, education, events and advertising	Training for professionals and families in healthy habits	Service-learning activities with theoretical-practical training (recipes and cooking techniques, menu planning, using food...), and community activities	Neighbourhood entities, schools, other organizations, restaurant professionals	Nº & type of learning activities People attending
Loss and waste of food and packaging	Raise awareness – on loss and waste of food and packaging	Organize cooking and nutrition workshops that also cover resource management – and household economy Recycling campaigns	Social entities and municipality	Nº & type of cooking workshops People attending
CITY-REGION				

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Information and narratives, education, events and advertising	Promote regulation of advertising	Limit and regulate unhealthy food and beverage advertising in public spaces and channels linked to municipal actions and neighbourhood agents, for example, in sports, public transportation, school environments, community events, or municipal media	City councils, public healthcare services (ICS), research, communication agencies	Elaboration of a municipal ban to limit unhealthy publicity in youth related environments; existence of unhealthy advertising around schools
Infrastructure for food communities	Promote accessibility and affordability of healthy and sustainable food fairly produced by improving local commerce and establishing mutual support networks that, at the same time, reinforcing local businesses	Study the commercial dynamics of neighbourhood residents as well as the reality of existing community networks, and facilitate participatory workshops among the involved actors to design and implement improvements in local commerce and in community networks	Caritas (NGO), FabLab Barcelona, Professional Council of Dietitians	Qualitative asseement of the study; amount of people/ organisations taking part in it; number of workshops; improvements implemented
Right to food, food justice, and food affordability	Improve food distribution systems through debit cards	Introduce improvements in the operation of the debit card service to transition towards a model that promotes the empowerment of the end users and the access to local, ecological, and seasonal resources, ensuring territorial equity. Starting from an initial assessment of demand volume and service cost, comparing existing models, and analysing impacts on health, well-being, economic sustainability of local producers and merchants, and autonomy of families.	Social supermarket and Department of Social Rights of the Government of Catalonia	TN° and type of improvements ; increase in the consumption of local & organic products
Information and narratives, education,	Disseminate messages of healthy and	Identify assets that act as "amplifiers" or opinion leaders in the community and promote	City Council, formal and informal educational centres,	Assets identified and scope of

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
events and advertising	sustainable eating among the local population	that they disseminate messages of healthy and sustainable food.	social entities, producers, religious centres, social and community assistance entities, restaurants, public facilities	community impacts; Type of messages promoted
Food sovereignty, empowerment and food diversity	Territorial re-agralization based on an agro-ecological model, promoting generational change and socio-community management	Agricultural contract that remunerates farmers and extensive livestock holders for the ecosystem services of their activity, leading to more affordable products and generating new jobs (e.g. with public procurement). Adaptation of crops to the planetary diet (e.g. to encourage greater consumption of legumes) by adapting to the climate and available soil, taking into account supply and demand. Establishing a public land bank. Promoting stronger urban-rural linkages such as public procurement of food with sustainability criteria. Promote cooperatives for joint procurement between residents and community agents.	Conreu Sereny (local farmers), Ecocentral/Alterbanc, Associació Vidasana (NGO for health promotion), ITA Salut Mental (healthcare service), AMB (administration), UOC, Institut Metròpoli, CREDA (research centres and universities)	Number of contracts Productive changes undertaken; Lands in bank land and total surface; Cooperatives support schemes

Lessons learned in Barcelona through the visioning & strategic planning process

While the implementation of each workshop has been more exigent and intensive in terms of workload than expected, the Barcelona Living Lab has accomplished two outcomes: On the one hand, being able to engage local citizens with the aims of FoodCLIC in each territory, also getting to better know, understand, tackle and take into account the reality and needs of each neighbourhood. On the other hand, the achievement of a good process of networking and learning for all participants.

Another interesting observation is that, even if each neighbourhood is very different in many regards, the approaches and proposed objectives and solutions to address the problems they face

related to their food environment were very similar, which provides an opportunity for the Living Lab to establish FPN connections between the different neighbourhoods' interventions.

Finally, the intensity of the FoodCLIC process in terms of number and high pace of workshops has become a filter by itself on the alignment of attendees to the FoodCLIC approach and principles. The participants that keep attending the different workshops were those who were getting committed and engaged in the process of creating a FPN and becoming change agents. However, participants from the private sector were still missing. Those that have been involved so far were always from organisations that have a dedicated social approach to their economic activities.

Finally, regarding the methodological approach, the system innovation methodologies have been useful to assure a systemic approach. However, we believe that more iterations for diagnosis and visioning will be needed, and it would be interesting to explore how to reflect on future scenarios that show visions that can be perceived more widely as more feasible.

BERLIN

Context for visioning and strategy workshops

The City of Berlin has adopted a municipal Food Strategy as an ongoing participatory process in collaboration with the Berlin Food Policy Council, a civil society network, starting in 2018. The political context for food transition work in Berlin changed in 2023, following a court-ordered repetition of city-wide and local district elections. The city government shifted from a Social Democrat-led coalition government with the Greens and Socialists to a Christian Democrat-led coalition government with the Social Democrats. In this process, responsibility for the city's food policies was transferred from the Senate Department for Environment, Climate and Consumer Protection, which had been led by a member of the Green Party, to the Department for Justice and Consumer Protection, led by a non-party senator nominated by the Christian Democrats. The composition of many district governments changed as well. In the surrounding federal state of Brandenburg, elections are scheduled for September 2024, with an expected shift towards the political right.

In this dynamic political context, the main organiser of the workshops and sense-making activities was the Berlin Food Policy Council (BFPC), a civil society association of actors who are committed to ecological, climate and socially just food production and distribution in the Berlin area. The BFPC sees itself as an alliance that publicly represents civil society positions and demands for a sustainable food system and wants to help them gain political recognition. As the practice partner in the Living Lab Berlin, the BFPC aims to focus political attention on inclusive food environments and the impact of food poverty.

Key challenges that affect these efforts include:

- Internal: comparatively low levels of volunteer engagement following the Covid-19 pandemic; precarious and insufficient funding, fully reliant on project applications;
- External: tightening public budgets and austerity; high inflation and cost of living; Berlin's migrant communities and economically disadvantaged citizens respond to interconnected events and global crises, such as the Turkish earthquake, the Russian war on Ukraine and the Israel-Gaza war; shifts in government following elections in Berlin and possibly in rural Brandenburg; different political majorities in the two sub-national governments (Berlin and Brandenburg) and in Berlin city district governments.

The FoodCLIC sense-making activities and the visioning & strategy workshops focused on 1) building a common understanding of food poverty and food environments that integrates knowledge and expertise in particular of social welfare, poverty, health and local community organisations, 2) building network collaboration on food policy and political dialog, and 3) building relations and collaboration with local citizens and migrant communities.

Sense-making activities

To provide a basis of joint sense making prior to the visioning & strategy workshops, the Berlin Living Lab started a process of network and dialogue building at neighbourhood, city and national level from early 2023. The spatial focus was on two neighbourhoods – **Rollberg** in the district of Neukölln, and **Falkenhagener Feld** in the district of Spandau. Using **one-to-one conversations** and numerous **community events** (including summer parties, neighbourhood cafés, community cookouts, school & classroom talks, etc.), the LL team engaged with local stakeholders and citizens. This process established new contacts and helped to kick-start dialog, deepened existing connections around food-related concerns and identified solutions with those working day-to-day in these communities. A community food mapping exercise at a weekly neighbourhood meeting (Café Mittwoch) documented food structures and challenges identified by the community and enabled feedback on different food environments.

Neighbourhood interactions were complemented by sense-making at Berlin and national level, including through focus groups with poverty and food bank networks, food retailers, and food

transition stakeholders, and participation in food poverty events and conferences in Berlin, Bonn and Dortmund. Lastly, two regular working groups were initiated: a quarterly food justice get-together, bringing in migrant voices, and a political roundtable which provides an open space for food poverty and policy actors to strategize, which has met twice at the time of writing.

Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops – Implementation & Outcomes

Visioning workshop participants
Photo: PFeindt

Brainstorming problems and solutions
Photo: AalHashemi

Implementation: The visioning workshop was held on 11th October 2023 at a hired event venue, followed by the Strategic Planning workshop on 17th January 2024 in a seminar room at Humboldt-Universität in the city centre. Participants at both workshops included food policy activists, city and district level administrators, community organisers, social welfare and poverty groups and academics.

The **visioning workshop** included 21 participants across sectors and followed an inclusive and consensus-oriented facilitation approach where ideas were solicited and discussed, but formal decision-making was not the purpose. The workshop method was designed to stimulate knowledge exchange and brainstorming with the program split into two sections: the morning featured plenary presentations. In the morning, Information was shared on food poverty statistics, health and social inclusion, structural and psychological factors of the food environment and key findings of the community food mapping and focus groups on food justice and food access; after lunch, stakeholder engaged in a facilitated discussion guided by two objectives: clarifying a common understanding of the key problems and discussing the desired outcomes for a future food system in Berlin. , One aspect considered in planning the format of the workshop was the potential uneven power dynamics and how to build open and inclusive participation – for example, holding space and time for deliberation amongst representatives who are often on the periphery of policy, and including presentation in the morning by a citizen representing her own experiences and perspectives of living with food insecurity and poverty.

Figure 5: Brainstorming notes from facilitated discussions in the visioning workshop in Berlin

In the period prior to and between the workshops, the Living Lab team went through a process of consultation (one-on-one-meetings with stakeholders and an internal review by the Berlin Food Policy Council) to draft criteria for the selection of interventions and a ‘building blocks’ document with strategic lines of action to address the key visions and goals of food system transformation.

Table 9: Participating organizations in the Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops in Berlin

STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP		VISIONING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Armutnetzwerk (Poverty Network)	Civil Society	Armutnetzwerk (Poverty Network)	Civil Society
Berliner Tafel (Berlin Food Bank)	Civil Society	Berliner Tafel (Berlin Food Bank)	Civil Society
Deutsche Umwelthilfe (German Environmental Defense Fund)	Civil Society	Diakonie (social service of the Evangelical churches)	Civil Society
Ernährungsrat Berlin (Berlin Food Policy Council)	Civil Society (2)	Verbraucherzentrale (consumer protection)	Civil Society (2)
Paritätische Verband (association of independent	Civil Society	AWO Bundesverband (workers' welfare association)	Civil Society

STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP		VISIONING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
welfare organizations, institutions and groups that carry out social work)			
Verbraucherzentrale (consumer protection)	Civil Society	Ernährungsrat Berlin (Berlin Food Policy Council)	Civil Society (2)
Quartiersmanagement Rollberg Kiez (neighbourhood management)	Civil Society/Government	Quartiersmanagement Rollberg Kiez (neighbourhood management)	Civil Society/Government
Senatsverwaltung für Justiz und Verbraucherschutz (Senate Department for Justice and Consumer Protection)	Government	Journalist	Other
Senatsverwaltung für Wissenschaft, Gesundheit & Pflege (Senate Department for Science, Health and Care)	Government	AG.URBAN (strategy development for urban space, housing and participation)	Private Sector
Bezirksamt Spandau (District Government)	Government	Agora Agrar (agricultural policy think tank)	Private Sector (2)
Charité (university hospital)	Research (2)	Senatsverwaltung für Justiz und Verbraucherschutz (Senate Department for Justice and Consumer Protection)	Government (2)
Food for Justice, Heidelberg University	Research	Bezirksamt Friedrichshain-Kreuzberg (District Government)	Government
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	Research (2)	Senatsverwaltung für Stadtentwicklung, Bauen & Wohnen (Senate Department for Urban Development, Building and Housing)	Government
		Universität Konstanz	Research
		Charité (university hospital)	Research (2)
		Food for Justice, Heidelberg University	Research
		Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin	Research (2)

The **Strategic Planning workshop** was then an opportunity for an in-person exchange and a culmination round of feedback and statements of support or amendments to the strategic plan. It was attended by 17 participants, some, but not all of which had participated in the Visioning workshops. This workshop followed a targeted discussion format in order to move forward from visioning to strategic action planning, with three distinct steps: presentation of action proposals developed from visioning results, in-depth discussion of proposals with space to express specific needs, interests, concerns and constructive feedback from participants and a wrap-up to collectively develop next steps and identify potential future involvement of participants in the strategic lines of action going forward.

Key understandings of food systems problems: The visioning workshop helped create a common understanding of all aspects of the food environment that impact people's food choice and key problems in the Berlin context. Participants contributed their system understanding and thereby helped prioritise determining factors for an improved food system. Problems which stood out were significant gaps in compelling evidence and accessible data on food poverty, the excluding effects of food poverty stigma, the impacts of social exclusion and food culture, and problematic marketing practices (online and offline) that perpetuate unhealthy food patterns and disguise the true and fair cost of food.

Vision for Berlin's future food system: In response to the common understanding of problems, a core vision evolved which focused on three areas: changing policy, changing public sentiment and creating infrastructure, all in the context of promoting inclusiveness, accessibility and visibility in the food environment. For a desirable future Berlin food system, participants in the workshop envisioned: improved data and information flow to understand and track food poverty and the experiences of those affected, positive advocacy to reduce food poverty stigma and include people suffering from food insecurity in the conversation, nurturing environments to support childhood nutrition and healthy diets (disrupting cycles described as "educate – motivate – medicate"); strict rules on food advertising, especially towards children and youth, and universal access across Berlin to infrastructure which should be considered 'critical' for life in a resilient city, i.e., free tap water, affordable public and private canteens, food banks, edible trees and gardens, regional supply chains and community-supported agriculture.

Participants endorsed and amended a set of criteria for interventions – as follows:

- at least two interventions are to be based in marginalised neighbourhoods
- they provide a window of opportunity where project resources can feasibly be leveraged to stimulate/impact food systems transformation in the city-region, guided by the following priorities:
 1. Increase the availability and affordability of regional fruit, vegetables and plant-based proteins;

2. Reduce the prevalence, advertising and pricing strategy of “junk” food and sugary drinks;
3. Test, evaluate or build inclusive concepts for easier access to regional, organic produce; or
4. Create or support initiatives or measures that strengthen the right to adequate food and re-establish access to food as a public good.

Strategic planning: In order to achieve the envisioned objectives for food poverty reduction and inclusive food environments in Berlin, the strategic planning outlined key lines of action that were identified as steps in an ongoing realization process. These actions revolve around key leverage points, including **reclaiming basic food services** and investments in public infrastructure and cooperation with private and commercial enterprises, for example to support increased public access to canteens and regional food procurement in large firms and businesses. Another set of levers engage public investments, economic planning, social welfare and fiscal policy to **affect the economy of production, retail price and basic welfare needs**. Last but not least, a **joint science-policy task force** should be established to tackle data and evidence gaps.

During the Strategic Planning Workshop, one of the strategic actions – **filling the data gap on food poverty in Berlin** – was highlighted as a common concern bridging both political and public awareness. It was suggested to pursue this topic through a real-life intervention in the project. A proposal for a **‘food poverty tracker’ for Berlin** was reviewed by workshop participants in terms of priorities and formulation of food poverty indicators in the context of complex food environments. Important dimensions to consider should include social participation and health indicators, as well as challenges in the recruitment and participation of vulnerable groups and households.

Anticipated challenges to realization: One of the biggest challenges identified by stakeholders during the strategic planning was the gap between conceptualising measures and their implementation. In the short term, data gaps and public communication can be improved, especially utilizing smaller pilot interventions as a learning ground for evidence on infrastructure and urban planning measures. More challenging, and less likely to be solved in the short term will be **securing buy-in and political will** which is needed to find resources for restructuring food environments – this includes difficulties securing support of politicians as well as mobilizing engagement in underprivileged neighbourhoods to take ownership in initiatives, for example food hubs or community gardens.

Table 10: Overview of results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process in Berlin

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES AND RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Reframing the discourse to destigmatize food poverty and make food environments visible	Create and communicate baseline data, reduce stigma to mobilize public and political attention	Food poverty data for Berlin Destigmatizing communication campaign	Research co-design with stakeholder input, i.e., consumer protection agency and districts, food banks	New data on food poverty No. of stakeholders in research process / public reach of campaigns
Right to Food and inclusive participation	Including voices and perspectives of vulnerable and marginalized groups in food and social policy	Establish right to food as relevant category for city policy and planning. Tailored political solutions and real-life interventions that include marginalised voices in the design	Cross-sectoral working group/task force in the institutions (city and district governments) & civil society roundtable with representatives of vulnerable/marginalized groups	Positive acknowledgement and impact on the content of public and media (new and conventional) debate and political planning and decision-making
Creating a resilient communal food (and water) infrastructure	Change scope and access to public food system infrastructure: e.g., free drinking water & fruit boxes and direct marketing from farm to community in public spaces and offices, open canteens, community food hubs, etc.	Preventative health services Culturally inclusive neighbourhood food hubs Accessible canteens and communal food services	Doctors' associations, local neighbourhood and community centres, initiatives and gardens, private businesses (large companies with canteens) & institutional food services	No. of households in the pilot areas accessing food hub/community kitchen Increased visibility and acceptance of fruit and vegetable options/supply Map of canteens & increased no. of canteens accessible to public
Reduce marketing that stimulates unhealthy eating habits	Restrictions on advertisement and regulations to prioritize transparency and public interest in marketing	Communal city planning	Urban planners and retail geographers, private food retailers and food services	New regulation on the location / online accessibility of food advertisements targeted to youth/children
Resilient (crisis-proofing) urban and regional food systems	Identify vulnerabilities of the city-region food system to potential shocks and crisis – re-establish direct and short-chain food supplies as 'critical' crisis infrastructure	Crisis preparedness Critical and resilient infrastructure for food environments	State policymakers and national Ministry of the Interior, regional agriculture and food retail associations, crisis and disaster management experts	Provisions in crisis management plan to identify local and regional food procurement as critical infrastructure

Lessons learned in Berlin through the visioning & strategic planning process

One of the 'lessons learned' from the workshops was that co-benefits, part of the CLIC framework, are useful to highlight – e.g. if public costs can be reduced by reducing food-related burdens on health care, or where reshaping food infrastructure towards fair and regional products also meets climate targets and international commitments. A more difficult aspect of the CLIC principles is linking rural and urban visions in each workshop and discussion, even when the reality is that system understanding depends on these interconnected visions and strategies. One goal in the future would be to closely examine where **currently missing economic and rural players** can be involved more intensively in collaboration, based first on securing attendance.

Challenges with representation and logistics did arise and provided further learning opportunities for the next steps and future events. Firstly, various challenges arose in terms of achieving **a steady and representative participation of marginalised groups** (reimbursement, other issues such as Turkish earthquake response, war in the Middle East, issues on affordable housing take priority) and we need to explore further strategies to create more reliability and consistency in attendance. Secondly, securing **attendance from the food industry, the business sector or representatives from alternative agriculture and large retailers** proved difficult. While these groups were invited, they declined to attend. Different aspects in attendance of companies met with difficulty, including (1) identifying the appropriate contact point in the respective retail bodies, (2) receiving BFPC endorsement for the necessity and purpose of exchange with the retailer, and (3) strategizing how to establish trustful and reciprocal exchange and interest on topics of food poverty and food environments.

BRASOV

Photo: Oprea Oana

Context for visioning and strategy workshops

The local food system has developed spontaneously over 30 years after the collapse of the food value chains that had been organized by communist structures before 1990. The meetings held in the period between September 2022 and November 2023 constituted an original and provocative element at the same time and enjoyed increasing interest from the actors of the food system. However, at the governmental level there is still no strategy for the development of the agri-food system, and aspects of co-benefits-linkages-inclusion-connectivity are addressed only sporadically and randomly. While the Brasov Metropolitan Agency has defined a sustainable development strategy for the Brasov metropolitan area, this does not include serious references to the agri-food system.

Given this situation, key challenges are to start the development of a special chapter on the food system in the metropolitan area. It was interesting to note that there are fragmented collaborations in the direction of education-business or governance-environment for professional reasons, but there are also examples of sustained collaborations motivated by the win-win philosophy. The upcoming political elections in 2024 could to some extent slow down the evolution of the FPNs at the local level, due to potential changes in the leadership of the actors in the area of governance. Furthermore, the dominance of large supermarkets makes small local producers feel uneasy with their participation.

Sense-making activities

Since spring 2023, a series of activities have been carried out which addressed the challenges of the food system in the region and the need to approach them with a comprehensive focus as proposed by the FoodCLIC project. Various stakeholders such as food sector professionals, entrepreneurs, civil society, and scientific researchers have participated in these activities.

Presentations have been given at several events, including international ones, as well as meetings with university alumni engaged in professional activities related to the food sector, with the aim to create synergies. Also, a series of events related to the signing of the agreement to participate in the Green Cities network were organized in Brasov, as well as events to popularize mountain food products on the occasion of the main holidays in Romania.

Table 14 Overview of sense-making activities leading up to Visioning & Strategic Planning

DATES	ACTIVITIES	TARGET GROUPS
Every 2 weeks	Meetings with former students, now employees of food companies (Olympus - Dairy factory; Prodlacta - dairy factory; Sergiana - meat producer; Selgros - supermarket; Metro food retail; Vel Pitar - bakery factory; Doripesco – fishery factory and restaurant; etc.), for exchanging experiences, creation of synergies and creation of common activities in the food sector for Brasov city region – Brasov, Romania	Business industry; Civil society
17-19 March 2023	GASTROPAN 2023: Presentation stand "Food Safety and Security in Romania" – Brasov, Romania;	Specialist in food sector; Business sector; Civil society
8 June 2023	Participation in the EHEDG seminar: Realities, opportunities, and challenges regarding food safety in Romania – Bucharest, Romania;	Food scientists; Business sector;
9 June 2023	Seminar Global Harmonization Initiatives – Bucharest, Romania;	Food Scientists; Business sector; Civil Society
22 Sept. 2023	Stakeholder Event: Valorisation of BlueBio Economy Resources for Food System - Trondheim, Norway	Food scientists; Business sector; Civil society
29 Sept. 2023	Researchers Night, 2023 – presentation stand FOODCLIC project - Brasov, Romania;	Food scientists; Business sector; Civil society
23-24 Nov. 2023	Participation in the Global Summit of Food and Health – Tainan, Taiwan	Food scientists; Business sector;

4-5 Dec 2023	Participation in conferences where seminars were organized on the topic of food futures, ex: Food 2030 - European Commission, Brussels, Belgium	Specialist in food sector; Civil society
8 Dec 2023	Online International Workshop: Cold chain and energy efficiency: future development; Organizer: NTNU and Sintef Energy - Trondheim, Norway	Food scientists; Business sector;

The activities undertaken within the project created new links of collaboration between stakeholders and dynamized the political class in addressing a very important food problem but left in the subsidiary plan. A very important element, an effect of the FoodCLIC implementation, is the inclusion of a special chapter in the sustainable development strategy of the Brasov Metropolitan area which explicitly addresses the issue of the agri-food system in Brasov.

Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops – Implementation & Outcomes

Implementation: The *visioning workshop* was held on the 10th of November 2023 at the Transilvania University. 54 actors were present from all over the quintuple helix, with representatives of both small and big business, the education sector, government representatives (city hall, the county statistics department, the direction of agriculture, etc), as well as environmental NGOs and representatives of the environmental protection agency. Other civil society organisations present included representatives from owners' associations and student associations.

Diverse methods and formats were used during the visioning workshop, including presentations of case studies from the mapping and gapping of city-region food systems, plenary lectures from experts across different sectors, facilitated break out group dialogs guided by visioning topics, and phases of open discussion and networking among participants. Presentations were shared that helped to clarify the current need to implement integrated food policies, as well as examples of past, present and future actions carried out by the municipality or other actors with experiences in projects related to food systems.

<i>Time schedule</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Location</i>
9.00 – 9.15	Registration participant	ICDT, Hall L2
9:15 – 10:00	FoodCLIC project presentation . Diagnosis of the food system in the Braşov Metropolitan Area	ICDT, Hall L2
10:00 – 11:00	Workshop: Challenges, opportunities of the food system in the Braşov Metropolitan Area	ICDT, Hall L2
11:00 – 11:15	Coffee break	ICDT, Room L2
11:15 – 13:00	Workshop: Perspectives of the food system in the Braşov Metropolitan Area	ICDT, Room L2
13:00 – 13:45	Lunch break	ICDT, Room L2
13:45 – 14:30	Conclusions. Networking	ICDT, Room L2

ICDT - Research and Development Institute of Transilvania University in Braşov
Address: Str. Institute No. 10 Brasov Romania

Figure 6 Program for the system understanding and visioning workshop

These different ways of communicating and formatting the visioning activities were used to engage diverse participants who come from different backgrounds, fields of training and levels of prior understanding of food system problems. Through these formats, the meeting sought to form a collective understanding of current problems and the necessary conditions for a vision of a harmonious future food system in Brasov city region. To ensure all perspectives were heard and considered, the opinions and questions of each participant were also requested in writing and note-taking throughout the event.

During the breakout groups, participants from each dimension of the helix had their own table where the actors could freely express their ideas in writing. These ideas were then shared and discussed in the workshop plenary session. During the wrap-up of the event, there was a need to extend the meeting time due to the amount of interest of some of the stakeholders to continue exchanging and networking.

The *Strategic Planning workshop* was held on 12th January 2024 at the Municipality Council Office and gathered relevant political figures such as the vice-mayor of the Brasov Municipality, the former director of Veterinary Health and Food Safety Department (DSVSA), the director of the Brasov markets administration, together with representatives of the Brasov metropolitan area, of the prefect and the Brasov county council; the county department of statistics, representatives of farmers, representatives of the social department from the municipality of Brasov, and teachers from the Faculty of Medicine and the Faculty of Food and Tourism, both from Transilvania University of Brasov.

The format of the strategic planning workshop was split into two main parts: in the first part, the workshop provided a follow-up summary from the visioning workshop and outlined the targeted objective of the second workshop - to focus on designing the strategic pathways towards each visioning goal. Discussion of these key topics from the visioning workshop - food security, food quality and lack of food education - was resumed and further developed among participants, many of which were present at both workshops.

The second part of the strategic planning workshop was focused on providing space for open discussions on the strategic objectives and actions, and the opportunity presented by the FoodCLIC project. Monitoring indicators were discussed and established for each individual strategic objective, such as monitoring the daily allocation of resources for citizens in public institutions, the number of organized mobile food markets, or the number of special spaces for local mountain food products in urban agri-food markets. This round of feedback and discussion was documented by facilitators in the form of meeting notes and minutes.

Table 15: Participating organizations in the Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshop in Brasov

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Institutia Prefectului Jud. Bv (Prefecture)	Government (2)	Primaria BV (Brasov Municipality)	Government (15)
Directia Jud. Pt Agricultura (County Directorate for Agriculture)	Government (2)	Unitbv (Transilvania Univ.) (Faculty of Medicine and Faculty of Food and Tourism)	Research and Education (5)
DSVSA (Veterinary Health and Food Safety Department)	Government	Unitbv Students Association	Civil Society (10)
DSP BV (Public Health Department)	Government (2)	SPAP (Agri-food Municipality Markets Administration)	Government (3)
Agentia de Plati si Interventie pt Agricultura BV (Payments and Intervention Agency for Agriculture Brasov)	Government (2)	Directia Jud. De Statistica (County Department of Statistics)	Government
Dir. Jud. De Statistica (County Department of Statistics)	Government	DSVSA (Veterinary Health and Food Safety Department)	Government
WWF Romania (World Fund for Nature)	Environment (2)	ROMO (Agricultural farmers)	Business
Asoc. De proprietari (Owners association)	Civil Society	La Chocolaterie Fresh SRL (HORECA)	Business
Highclere Consulting (Project Consulting)	Business (2)	AMB (Brasov Metropolitan Agency)	Government
Primaria BV (Brasov Municipality)	Government (6)	Le Fru Marin (Meat Processing Factory)	Business
Unitbv (Transilvania University) (Faculty of Medicine and Faculty of Food and Tourism)	Research and Education (5)	Highclere Consulting (Project Consulting)	Business

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Unitbv Students Association	Civil Society (9)	Institutia Prefectului Jud. Bv (Prefecture)	Government
Doripesco (Fish farm)	Business	Rose Story (Farmers)	Business
Selgros (Hypermarket)	Business	Consiliul Jud. Brasov (Brasov County Council)	Government
Rose Story (Farmers)	Business	Directia de Asistenta BV – Caminul pentru varstnici (Nursing Directorate Brasov – Home for the elderly)	Government
ADASTRO SRL (Food producer)	Business	Serviciul achizitii publice (Public procurement service)	Government (3)
Colegiul Tehnic M. Baiulescu (College)	Research and Education	Directia arh. Sef (Chief Architect Department)	Government (2)
ROMO (Agricultural farmers)	Business (2)		
APM (Agency for Environment Protection)	Government (2)		
Gloria Jeans Coffee Brasov (HORECA)	Business		
AMDDTP BV (Brasov Metropolitan Agency)	Government (3)		
Liceul de Arte Plastice Hans Mattis-Teutsch (College)	Research and Education		
MacDonalds Brasov	Business		
Intersnack (snack food company)	Business		
SAB Team SRL (Distribution of food products)	Business		

Key understandings of food system problems: Food system understanding was limited to the area of work/interest of the respective stakeholders. On the other hand, there were important barriers to make progress on common understandings, such as lack of time, lack of trust in real changes or the fear of having to share confidential information about the own organization.

Vision for Brasov's future food system: The main three topics addressed were related to:

- 1) *Food security*, where the low daily amount allocated for institutionalized citizens was noted, such as the need to improve citizens' access to cheaper agri-food markets.
- 2) *Food quality*, where issues such as the dominance of big food chains over small local suppliers on local markets was raised as a concern. Given the existence of quality food products from local agro-tourism farms, improving access to them was proposed through the organization of special spaces in urban agri-food markets.
- 3) *Lack of education* regarding the importance of food for health, which could be addressed through educational workshops with qualified staff.

Strategic planning: Building on the visioning results, five lines of intervention were discussed:

- Related to food security, the low daily amount allocated for **institutionalized citizens** was noted. Here it was proposed to increase this amount through a decision by the local council. In addition, to improve citizens' access to cheaper agri-food markets, it was suggested to organize either adequate transport routes to such **markets or flying markets in disadvantaged neighborhoods**.
- Another topic addressed was related to the access to **local food products**. Currently, the food market in Brasov is dominated by big food chains (Metro, Selgros, Carrefour, Kaufland, Lidl, etc.) where local products have difficult access. Given the existence of quality food products from local agro-tourism farms, it was proposed to improve access to them through the organization of **special spaces in urban agri-food markets**.
- Related to the lack of education in nutrition and health, it was proposed to organize **workshops and seminars** in the academic and research environment, with guests from the areas of food and medicine.
- Furthermore, a need was identified to develop a **special chapter on the sustainable development of the Brasov agri-food system** within the document: "Sustainable development strategy of the Brasov Metropolitan area".
- Since there is no clear strategy for the harmonious inclusion of the rural areas adjacent to Brasov, it was proposed to create a **legislative framework to preserve the green areas** in the peri-urban area.

Main barriers: The main barriers to the proposed strategies referred to the **upcoming elections** in 2024, which could change the political colour of the decision-makers. For this reason, in the coming months an important objective would be to **formalize the FPN** and its role in the decisions of the municipality. Furthermore, important elements to overcome in the Brasov reality are **ensuring a safe space** for every stakeholder so that anyone can speak up and share their concerns, needs and problems on an equal base, and assuring everybody that their time is not wasted, and that the implication of each and every one of them is very well needed and equally important.

Table 16: Overview of results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process in Brasov

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Food security (Inclusion)	Decreasing the number of food deprived families	Increasing allocated sum for daily meal in social houses in Brasov	Brasov Local Council	- The amount of funds allocated per day per person
Food security (Inclusion)	Improving the access of citizens to more affordable agri-food markets	Organising flywheel markets in food-deprived neighbourhoods	Brasov municipality	- No. of markets organised - Consumer feedback questionnaires
Linkage rural-urban	Improving the quality of food in the Brasov city-region	Organising local food stalls in the main agri-food markets	Brasov municipality	- No. of markets organised - Consumer feedback questionnaires
Lack of education in nutrition & health	Increasing awareness about the influence of nutrition on health	Organising meetings in academia for debates about nutrition and health	Education partners (universities and high schools)	- No. of participants - Feedback questionnaires
Lack of political programs regarding agri-food system	Developing a sustainable and inclusive agri-food system in the Brasov city-region	Elaboration of a special chapter in the Brasov Metropolitan Area Sustainable Development Strategy	Brasov Metropolitan Area	- Document elaborated and adopted
Strategy regarding the urban expansion toward rural area	Preserving green resources from peri-urban area	Adjusting urban development plan	Brasov municipality	- Local Council decision

Lessons learned in Brasov through the visioning & strategic planning process

The most efficient working method were plenary discussions, followed by individual written collection of participants' ideas and suggestions. It was interesting to note the motivation of actors from the economic environment to participate with innovative ideas and proposals, as well as the help provided by their experience in other projects. The organization of the strategy workshop right in the town hall's council room was a special boost for the participants, demonstrating their trust in the mayor's institution. Expectations regarding the participation of civil society actors were not fully met, so that before the next meetings the team will insist by phone that they should present their important role in the FPN. Looking back, it would have been important to allocate more time to free discussions between the actors of the food system, which is obvious in hindsight, considering that the FPN initiative is a novelty for Romania.

BUDAPEST

Photo: ESSRG

Context for visioning and strategy workshops

In March 2023, the Municipality of Budapest launched the **formal Food Policy Network (FPN) of Budapest**. One of the main objectives of this forum is to bring together all stakeholders directly involved in the food chains in and around the capital in a farm-to-table approach. Participants can share their knowledge and experience to support and shape the development of a sustainable food policy for the capital city and formulate the objectives of the **Integrated City Food Strategy**. The long-term aim of the forum is to create a collaborative network that can generate the necessary attention and resources at the city-region level to implement policies to successfully develop sustainable urban food systems. Access to the network is open, and different stakeholders and organizations can join continuously. At the time of reporting, 25 organizations have expressed their interest and motivations behind their involvement (see Figure 1). The list of organizations who have expressed their interest include, among others, the Ministry of Agriculture, the National Public Health Centre, the Association of Conscious Consumers, the Hungarian Food Bank Association, the Association of Responsible Food Producers, Solidarity Economy Center, Bedrock.farm, Eutropian, The Hungarian Hospitality Employers' Association, Hungarian Society of

Nutrition, and several district municipalities of Budapest. With the city moving towards signing the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP), the activities in the FoodCLIC project could contribute to system understanding around the categories of the MUFPP.

Table 74: Motivations of members of the Food Policy Network Budapest

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Influence and policy change • Networking and knowledge-building • Rural-urban linkages • Addressing daily challenges • Research and innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing good practices • Promotion of short food chains • Research alignment to local needs • Creating new collaborative spaces
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Key challenges: There are three main challenges in developing and implementing an integrated food policy in Budapest city-region:

- First, inclusiveness and engaging with diverse participants brings potential differences in visions and goals, requiring compromise over a longer-term process.
- Second, in most cases, vulnerable groups, including food insecure people, farmers, homeless people, and people with health problems, have only been involved indirectly through organizations.
- Finally, the Budapest Living Lab is constantly battling against legal (dual local authority system in Budapest) and political obstacles (the national government centralizes tasks and responsibilities from local level, increasing political tensions between the government and municipalities).

FPN formation has been spearheaded by the **Mayor's Office of Budapest**, which will develop the network's operational plan, objectives, possible working groups, leaders, and competencies and network expansion. They will also examine (with the help of a legal expert) how to integrate an FPN working group into the functioning of the Office and the Municipality of Budapest. However, there is an increasing **political tension between the government and municipalities**. While mayor's offices, including the Mayor's Office of Budapest, are politically neutral institutions, many people still associate this administration and FPN activities with the municipal (leading party) label.

Sense-making activities

Joint sense-making activities built upon the work of the Budapest Living Lab research partners Environmental Social Science Research Group (ESSRG). The mapping and gapping activities in the first phase of the FoodCLIC project captured further perspectives on food system challenges in Budapest, on necessary changes, and the role of various stakeholders in this process. ESSRG conducted 17 semi-structured interviews within the different departments of the Municipality of Budapest, the Mayor's Office of Budapest and among companies overseen by the Municipality.

Their capacities, barriers, and gaps were assessed to understand current and potential roles in creating a healthy, just, inclusive, and sustainable food strategy in the capital city-region.

Based on joint sense-making results, three main conclusions can be drawn:

- First, there is a lack of information about food-related topics in the Municipality, a general lack of knowledge about the challenges the city faces in the food system, and a lack of capacity within the departments and what role they can or should play in developing the strategy.
- This includes gaps in knowledge exchange between departments. For example, the Municipality of Budapest and the Mayor's Office departments were unaware that the Department for Climate and Environmental Affairs had started to focus on food-related projects and that a food strategy was being drafted within the context of FoodCLIC.
- There is a need for a strong coordinating role in the collaboration of many different disciplines in the city hall, including employees in the Department for Climate and Environmental Affairs, which allows for feedback and exchange on similar and overlapping goals.

Considering these findings, the following learning questions offered a frame for further investigation and collective reflection in visioning and strategic planning workshops:

- How do we raise the visibility of FoodCLIC within the city and the strategic importance of food as an issue?
- How do we raise awareness of the links between food-related challenges at the city level and the work of individual departments? How can the strategic plan for transforming the food system be integrated into the work of each department?
- How can this coordination capacity be used for food system transformation?

Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops – Implementation & Outcomes

Implementation: A 3-hour **visioning workshop** took place on 6th November 2023 at "Európa Pont", a facility in the city of Budapest that can be used for holding workshops of EU-funded projects free of charge. The promotion of the workshop by a combination of email invitations and email and

telephone reminders attracted 50 online registrations prior to the workshop, with a total of 38 participants from diverse backgrounds (retail sector, national authorities, civil society organizations, researchers, farmers) finally attending (see Table 1). While every sector of the stakeholder matrix was represented, the most numerous groups were civil society and research and academia, while the least represented were national authorities and actors from the retail sector. The visioning was framed around food environments in the year 2050, with participants choosing breakout groups on the specific food environment which most interested them, and connections made to each category of the MUFPP. After discussing each topic, facilitators summarized the visions and main focal points, and participants used dotmocracy to explore input from other tables and vote for ideas. One of the additional purposes of the workshop was to encourage participants to join the FPN in future collaboration which would be stimulated by FoodCLIC but sustainable after the project lifetime.

Key understandings of food systems problems: First, participants noted the challenge to address fake information circulating in public concerning healthy and sustainable foods. Second, they agreed that the current system, being for-profit, encourages consumers to eat unhealthy/junk food thanks to advertisements and lack of adequate food literacy. Third, they articulated the problem of having too many middlemen selling goods at markets, making supply chains longer and making it harder for consumers to decide what is locally produced sustainable food and what is not. Consequently, participants also stressed that there was a lack of regulation and adequate monitoring systems which could contribute to the elimination of food fraud.

Vision for Budapest's food system in 2050: In response to these challenges, participants envisioned educating pupils through incorporating food literacy in school curricula, and informing the public through a platform for sharing knowledge and information backed up by scientific facts concerning healthy, locally produced, sustainable food. Furthermore, participants envisioned strengthening urban-rural linkages by supporting farmers' markets in municipally owned spaces to sell regional goods, complimented by regulatory frameworks to prioritize smallholder farmers' interests. Moreover, in the future vision of the city, green spaces within the centre and in the wider city-region of Budapest will be producing food and educating generations of residents. Overall, participants reflected on the need to change the perspective about food from a for-profit economy to a common good.

Figure 7: Illustration based on Visioning Workshop, Credit: Emőke Holbis

Strategic planning: The strategic planning workshop took place on the morning of 9 January at the City Hall of Budapest with 43 participants selected based on the Quadruple Helix (indicated here as government, business, research, and civil society), focusing on members whose areas of expertise are expected to be included in the integrated food strategy.

Table 15: Participating organizations in the Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshop in Budapest

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Nemzeti Népegészségügyi és gyógyszerészeti Központ (National Centre for Public Health and Pharmacy)	Government (2)	Budapest Közút Zrt. (Public Roads Ltd.)	Government (2)
Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Klíma- és Környezetügyi Főosztály (Department for Climate and Environmental Affairs, Mayor's Office)	Government (3)	TÉT Platform (Nutrition Platform)	Civil Society

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Közbeszerzési és Projektmenedzsment Főosztály (Procurement and Project Management Department, Mayor's Office)	Government	MÁV Zrt. (State Railways)	Government
Budapesti Módszertani Szociális Központ és Intézményei (Budapest Methodological Centre of Social Policy and Its Institutions)	Government	Budapesti Nagybani Piac Zrt. (Wholesale Market)	Business (2)
Agri Kulti Nonprofit Kft. (Research Company)	Research	Budapest Főváros Városépítési Tervező Kft (City Construction Design)	Government (3)
InDeRe Élelmézkutató és Innovációs Intézet (Food Research and Innovation Institute)	Research	Nemzeti Népegészségügyi és gyógyszerészeti Központ (National Centre for Public Health and Pharmacy)	Government (4)
HUN-REN BTK Néprajztudományi Intézet (Institute for Ethnology)	Research	Agri Kulti Nonprofit (Research Company)	Research
Szolidáris Gazdaság Központ (Solidarity Economy Centre)	Research	VIMOSZ (Hospitality Employers' Association)	Business
Eutropian (Urban Research Group)	Research	HUN-REN BTK Társadalomtudományi Kutatóközpont Szociológiai Intézete (Centre for Social Sciences)	Research (2)
Ökológiai Mezőgazdasági Kutatóintézet (Research Institute of Organic Agriculture)	Research	Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Közbeszerzési és Projektmenedzsment Főosztály (Procurement and Project Management Department, Mayor's Office)	Government
Magyar Táplálkozástudományi Társaság (Hungarian Society of Nutrition)	Research	Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Klíma- és Környezetügyi Főosztály (Department for Climate and Environmental Affairs, Mayor's Office)	Government (3)
Budapest Gazdasági Egyetem (Budapest Business University)	Research	Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Kulturális, Turisztikai, Sport és Ifjúságpolitikai Főosztály (Sport and Youth Department, Mayor's Office)	Government (3)
Budapest Bike Maffia (Food donation)	Civil Society (2)	Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Várostervezési Főosztály, Tájépítészeti Osztály (Department of Urban Planning/Landscape Architecture Division, Mayor's Office)	Government

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Common Jam (urban gardening)	Civil Society (2)	Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Főjegyzői Iroda (Chief Clerk's Office, Municipality of Budapest)	Government
Magyar Élelmiszerbank Egyesület (Hungarian Food Bank Association)	Civil Society	HUN-REN BTK Néprajztudományi Intézet (Institute for Ethnology)	Research
Magyar Természetvédők Szövetsége (ational Society of Conservationists – Friends of the Earth Hungary)	Civil Society	InDeRe Élelmézkutató és Innovációs Intézet (Food Research and Innovation Institute)	Research (2)
Felelős Gasztrohős Alapítvány (Heroes of Responsible Dining Foundation)	Civil Society	Greenpeace	Civil Society
Greenpeace	Civil Society	MET "Fűtött utca" (Evangelical Fellowship)	Civil Society
Átalakuló Wekerle – Átalakuló Közösségek Transition Wekerle - Transition Communities	Civil Society	Szolidáris Gazdaság Központ (Solidarity Economy Center)	Research
Turisztikai és Vendéglátó Munkaadók Országos Szövetsége (VIMOSZ) (Hungarian Hospitality Employers' Association)	Business	Budapesti Módszertani Szociális Központ és Intézményei (Budapest Methodological Centre of Social Policy and Its Institutions)	Government
MagosVölgy Kft. (farm)	Business	Magyar Élelmiszerbank Egyesület (Hungarian Food Bank Association)	Civil Society
Budapest Vásárcsarnokai Kft. (Budapest Market Halls Ltd.)	Business	BKM Nonprofit Zrt. FŐKERT (Public Utilities / Urban Park Management)	Government (2)
Pipacs Pékség Kft. (Pipacs Bakery Ltd.)	Business	Magyar Természetvédők Szövetsége (ational Society of Conservationists – Friends of the Earth Hungary)	Civil Society
Nestlé Hungária Kft.	Business (2)	Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Főpolgármester-helyettesi Iroda (Deputy Mayor's Office)	Government
Farm2Fork Kft.	Business	Budapest Főpolgármesteri Hivatal Szociálpolitikai Főosztály (Department for Social Policy, Mayor's Office)	Government
Remény Farm (Hope Farm)	Business	Budapest Global (Urban Stakeholders in Business Sector)	Business
Csoroszlya Farm Kft.	Business	FAO (European and Central Asian Regional Office)	Government
		Eutopian (Urban Research Group)	Research

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
		Magyar Táplálkozástudományi Társaság (Hungarian Society of Nutrition)	Research
		Kislépték Egyesület (Association of Interest Representation for Small-scale Producers and Service Providers)	Civil Society

To set the stage for strategic planning, a historian provided a perspective on Budapest's food policies 100 years ago. This presentation played an important role at the workshop, showing good practices to the city administration, including the vice mayor who had opened the workshop, and laying the foundations for subsequent work. The overall objective of the workshop was to establish the major points for the content of Budapest's food strategy and to think collaboratively in working groups on the key topics of municipal departments with food as a cross-cutting issue: environmental sustainability and food; living environment & urban development and food; local economy and food; education and food; and health and food.

Key points of each working group were documented, then evaluated and ranked by the other groups based on two factors: Which ideas did they find most important, and which did they think were most easy to implement? Ranking and voting processes helped prioritize ideas for further planning of food strategy measures and project interventions. Different aspects of strategic planning for each measure were developed during the workshop exercises, including human resources and professional knowledge, financial resources, communication plans, risk management plans, success criteria and benchmarks, and monitoring. The results were collected and shared with participants for further feedback and validation. Proposed food strategy measures included regulatory actions, reconsidering the role of market halls and communal food processing centres, and logistical reconsideration of the Danube River for food trade and transport solutions (see full list in Supplementary Material 1: Proposals for Budapest Food Strategy). Examples of actions which were considered urgent and most implementable were related to green procurement, urban gardening and farming, *Veganuary* campaigning and saving surplus food in supply chains.

During the discussion, the topic of competencies and the participation of the subdistricts in the capital, and chamber of commerce on agriculture emerged as a dilemma. Given the fact that small producers alone often cannot produce enough to meet the purchasing needs of the capital or other customers in terms of quantity, the task of coordinating and bringing together small producers was highlighted, as well as the need to work with small producers economically and legally, for example through tendering public contracts.

Overall, the evaluation of the suggestions collected during the strategy workshop showed that the highest importance was placed on the education of children and parents together, from kindergarten-age onwards, with dedicated advocacy to target vulnerable communities, for example in school canteens, urban gardens and street food festivals. In creating awareness campaigns, the need was noted for independent nutrition professionals to carry out activities, in light of a current dominance of the business sector in advertising to shape public attitudes on healthy eating.

Anticipated challenges to realization: One key challenge to developing an action plan for Budapest is the lack of experience of the majority of participants in food-related policies and strategies. However, despite this **limited expertise**, there was a clear enthusiasm for the task. The workshops were one of the first steps for most invitees towards food system transformation. Hence, further concrete goals, such as establishing the timeline of the strategic plan, will require continued discussions. So far, **no consensus** has been reached on timeline, scope, and path to establish the dedicated personnel required to reach these goals. One challenge was clear: the biggest shortage is in human resources – lacking professionals with enough sense of responsibility and expertise. Other obstacles to the achievement of the strategic objectives are **the lack of policies, data and knowledge** at both the level of the population and the municipalities.

Table 16: Overview of results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process in Budapest

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Food education and literacy	Raise public health awareness Joint education of children and parents Implementing food education in school curriculum	Creation of educational campaigns online/offline for the public on food-related topics Making canteens a space for education	Individual experts (e.g. dietitians), schools and school canteens, teachers and educators	Assessment of public knowledge, reduction of food-related illnesses, increase of healthy food consumption
Strengthening local rural-urban linkages	The expansion of urban agriculture, elimination of middlemen on municipally owned markets and shortening supply chain	Development of green procurement practices and requirements, targeted tenders for local farmers and a regulatory environment that supports local food production, urban agriculture and self-sufficiency, developing	Economic empowerment and involvement of small producers	Increase of local producers in the supply chain, increase the volume of sales of locally sourced products

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
		incentives for local food production		
Transparency and knowledge dissemination	Informing the public about the work of the future FPN and combating fraudulent information concerning sustainable and healthy food	Comprehensive analysis and data collection: a comprehensive study integrating various aspects of the food supply sector in the capital city	The coordinating role of the municipality of the capital	
Food production & food waste	Re-evaluation of current regulatory frameworks, allowing more flexibility	Food rescue from markets (donating surplus to vulnerable people)	Markets run by the municipality of the capital, vendors, district residents, NGOs, local authorities and social workers	The amount of rescued food and the diversity of food is growing. More places take part in food saving activities
Rethinking legal frameworks and regulatory environment	Green Procurement policy (food as an integrated aspect)	Changing the legal and regulatory environment, finding a legal solution supporting small-scale farmers in the city region, influencing public procurement processes towards quality	Coordination of farmers, organization of food pre-processors	Increase of the volume of local products in public procurement

Lessons learned through the visioning & strategic planning process in Budapest

Overall, participants expressed their joy about the opportunity to engage and work together with professionals from other areas of expertise around food issues. Budapest has strong traditions in the city administration regarding food systems, but these traditions have not been practiced in the past 100 years. The enthusiasm will need to be continuously cultivated to ensure that progress continues following the workshops. One feedback from participants was to create even more time and space for networking, as a motivating factor in future events. Both the visioning and strategic planning combined workshops with optional networking lunches, for example.

There were also certain sectors and organizations that were missing from the process or did not take up the invitation to attend, and will need further targeted engagement, i.e., trade unions and the **business sector** more generally. Where there were anticipated issues of debate or controversies – for example on the role of the consumption of animal-based food in school

canteens – it was helpful to utilize professional facilitators, who were briefed on methods and strategies for equitable deliberation, such as:

- Ensuring everyone contributes to the discussion: Each participant had to write their thoughts on a post-it and introduce it to others while sticking it on the cartons.
- Creating a safe space: Participants were encouraged not to judge each other's opinions but to explore the wide range of perspectives on a topic.
- Ensuring balanced discussions: Facilitators intervened if a participant dominated the conversation excessively.
- Utilizing dotmocracy: Participants could express their opinion in various forms. Through this method, everyone gets the same amount of “voting power” over a topic and less dominant stakeholders could also express their opinions easily.

Regarding the CLIC framework, it was interesting to experience that the facilitators did not have to put much effort into implementing these aspects, as they came up during the discussions organically at each work section.

CAPANNORI, PLAIN OF LUCCA

Photo: Arianna De Conno

Context for visioning and strategy workshops

The four municipalities **Capannori, Altopascio, Porcari and Villa Basilica** are forming a coordinated and participatory **food policy management initiative** called “Piana del Cibo”. This initiative, active in the Plain of Lucca, aims to increase the well-being of people living in the area and to promote sustainable development.

At the time of the exploratory mapping and gapping activities of the FoodCLIC project, by the third quarter of 2022, the Food Policy Piana del Cibo, experienced a phase in which all coordinated activities had slowed down – due partly to Covid-19 and partly to political changes. While initiatives at local level had continued and, in some cases, found new mechanisms for moving forward (e.g. sustainable reorganization of school canteens while adapting to Covid-19 restrictions at the municipality of Capannori), the main challenges included the continuation of coordinated actions and participatory discussions – despite the existence of a complex governance structure for enabling participation which characterizes this intermunicipal Food Policy. By the beginning of 2023, overarching visioning and strategizing processes needed to be restarted, especially at the level of the public administrations involved. Representatives from local initiatives felt the need to hear again from the administration and food policy representatives.

Sense-making activities

The Living Lab Capannori/Plana di Lucca held different meetings in April and June 2023, which were crucial to begin developing a shared working methodology. These meetings served both to understand the political situation regarding food policy, to share the results of the mapping and

gapping work developed by FoodCLIC in the area, and to begin coordinating the vision and strategic planning workshops.

Within the framework of these meetings, there was a need to **restart the Food Policy** by renewing the active commitment of public administrations and focusing actions on specific key themes and initiatives, rather than restarting multiple working groups, at least concerning the participation of the political components of the Food Policy Network (FPN). It was decided to align the next key actions with other activities that were being organized at the territorial level by other actors of the FPN, particularly Slow Food.

The main achievements were the restart of the dialogue among four of the five municipalities involved (as the Municipality of Lucca, initially part of the FPN, withdrew from the initiative) and the joint planning of a series of events with the involvement of several civil society organizations in October 2023. The main identified challenge continued to be related to the issue of participation, particularly with questions about how to expand participation in food policy discussions (for example, what can attract new people in the long term? How can the FPN concretely add to existing activities on the ground?) and ensure its long-term continuity.

Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops – Implementation & Outcomes

Poster Municipality of Capannori

Photo: A. De Conno

Photo: Arianna De Conno

Implementation: The *visioning workshops* were held on the 8th and the 13th October 2023. They were embedded into public events **as part of the initiative Slow Beans**, organised by Slow Food in partnership with the Municipality of Capannori. They were structured in three sessions: the first one in the morning of 8th October, with representatives from the four municipalities of the FPN, together with the local mayors and the president of the Piana del Cibo. Here, the results from the mapping and gapping exercise were presented and validated, to then discuss which key issues should be addressed with priority. In this visioning session, the Living Lab also presented regional maps resulting from the participatory mapping and gapping activities and invited the audience to add comments with pins and post-its, creating a living map (see figure 1).

The second visioning session, during the afternoon of the same day, gathered representatives from non-profit organisations including local community gardens and food aid distribution

networks. The format was an open knowledge exchange to create collective reflection on the connections between their current work, potential benefits of better coordination and a more networked approach to action, and lessons learned from the experiences of those who had participated in Piana del Cibo in the past. Facilitators of this session noted down key words from the discussion and wrote them on a board, which was later used as a visual tool to form the basis of the wrap-up discussion at the close of the workshop. The aim of this method was to produce an understanding of the impact of these civil society organisations on the regional food system and food policy and envision how their effectiveness could be enhanced through improved coordination.

Finally, the third session was held on 13th October 2023, gathering speakers from other regions or organisations. It focused on the development of food policies at national level. This was another event that was open to the public, and this focus of discussion was the contributions and insights of external speakers from other Italian regions. Speakers were invited to reflect on guiding questions developed by the Living Lab as well as to respond to questions and remarks from the audience.

Photo: A. De Conno

Figure 7. Living maps used in the visioning workshop; participants were invited to add notes and comments in relation to their food environment and land use in the surrounding city-region

The *strategic planning workshops* were also organized in the frame of Slow Beans 2023, and split into three sessions in the area of Capannori. The first session, on October 20th, was a food education workshop around local beans production. It addressed children in a primary school in Capannori, involving children, teachers, an external food education and nutrition expert, the

University of Pisa and representatives from the FPN. The second workshop was held on October 21st, 2023, and focused on public canteens and sustainable public food procurement strategies. It brought together local stakeholders directly involved in local supply chains and experts, public servants, and local inhabitants. Thirdly, strategic planning occurred as part of a conference meeting on 27th October 2023 which focused on the protein transition and the connections between current agricultural production patterns and the possibilities for reorienting diets towards more sustainable patterns. It involved experts such as academics from University of Pisa, CSO and NGO representatives, and local inhabitants.

Figure 8 FoodCLIC workshops integrated into the calendar of Slow Beans 2023 events

The connection between the strategic action planning and the outputs of the visioning sessions occurred on several levels. First, thematically: at the centre of the discussion was the topic of sustainable diets and protein transition, starting from the public, private and civil society experiences in the area. Secondly, methodologically, these events were also organized in the frame of Slow Beans 2023 which enabled highly interactive and engaging formats that included both discussion and enjoyment of shared food experiences.

In the first strategic session, for example, the vision of improved primary school food education was the basis to start testing a strategic action: piloting and potentially expanding the concept of a food education lab. The format of this strategic session aimed to engage participants in dialog around protein transition in relation to local traditional food recipes and locally produced beans. The school children present at the event were invited to taste a traditional soup as well as reflect on the origins of beans, their properties and do some visual activities - such as gathering images and developing drawings in relation to the characteristics of local beans production. A key

component of this workshop was the idea to involve parents as much as possible – for example, by sharing with children some beans to be brought back home.

Linking the FoodCLIC workshops into the Slow Beans events allowed to anchor the intervention as part of ongoing activities on the ground, and to effectively engage the municipality of Capannori and the Living Lab members. In this way – and thanks to visibility and communication strategy for this series of events – the workshops were accessible to a wider audience as well as experts from outside the area.

The table below lists the key participants (speakers and main intervenors) to the workshops. As most of these events were also open to the public, more people attended as part of the audience, mainly local inhabitants (civil society and local small businesses).

Table 86: Participating organizations in the Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops in Capannori/Piana di Lucca

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOPS	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
8 th October 2023		20 th October 2023	
Municipality of Capannori	Public administration	Lunata School children	School children – civil society
Municipality of Altopascio	Public Administration	C. Barzanò	Expert in food education – research
Municipality of Porcari	Public Administration	Municipality of Capannori	Public Administration
Municipality of Villa Basilica	Public Administration	University of Pisa	Research
Plana del Cibo	Public Administration/Civil Society	Piana de Cibo	Public Administration/Civil Society
University of Pisa	Research	Slow Food Lucca Compitese e Orti Lucchesi	Civil Society
ASL Toscana nord-ovest		21 st October 2023	
Frantoio sociale del Compitese	Social Business	Municipality of Capannori	Public Administration
Frantoio sociale la Visona	Social Business	Municipality of Altopascio	Public Administration
Confagricoltura	Business Association	Municipality of Porcari	Public Administration
Ass. Presepe vivente di Ruota	Civil Society	Municipality of Villa Basilica	Public Administration
CIA Toscana Nord	Business Association	Plana del Cibo	Public Administration/Civil Society

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOPS	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Mulino Germolli	Civil Society	University of Pisa	Research
Cooperativa sociale Calafata	Social Business	ANCI Toscana	Public Administrations' Association
Coldiretti	Business Association	CIR Food	Public Canteens Manager
Tuscany Region	Public Administration	Dal Monte Ristorazione	Public Canteens Manager
Slow Food Lucca Compitese e Orti Lucchesi	Civil Society	Qualità e Servizi	Public Canteens Manager
Cooperativa Sociale Odissea	Social Business	Giubilesi & Associati	Public Canteens Monitoring Society
Caritas di Lucca	Civil Society	Public Canteens School Commission	School parents – Civil Society
Legambiente Capannori e Piana	Civil Society	27 th October 2023	
Associazione micologica gruppo "Massimiliano Danesi"	Civil Society	Slow Food Italia	Civil Society
Accademia degli infarinati	Civil Society	Laboratorio Sismondi	Research
Ass. Castanicoltori	Civil Society	Pisa University	Research
Strada del Vino e dell'Olio Lucca, Montecarlo, Versilia	Business Association	Palermo University	Research
13 th October 2023		Meatless Monday	Civil Society
Municipality of Capannori	Public Administration	Center for a Livable Future – John Hopkins University	Research
Slow Food Italia	Civil Society		
Slow Food Toscana	Civil Society		
Piana del Cibo	Public Administration/Civil Society		
ANCI Toscana	Public Administrations' Association		
Piemonte Region	Public Administration		

CRFS problems highlighted were the following: the progressive decreasing of local agricultural activities and ensuing agricultural land abandonment or conversion; the impoverishment of vulnerable population strata (particularly visible during the COVID-19 related socio-economic crisis) and their lack of access to healthy/quality food. It is important to note that the latter issues related to vulnerable groups, while being mentioned, were not particularly at the centre of the previous work of the Piana del Cibo network. The discussion rather focused on the visions around the role and scope of the FPN, which most participants were already familiar with.

Vision for Capannori and Plain of Lucca's future food system generally revolved around the right to food, via the promotion of local agricultural production, and the idea of rebuilding a sense of community. The great agricultural past of this area was mentioned as an example not to forget, both in terms of the richness of local food culture and food sovereignty. Other main themes included: (1) the need to enhance (existing) integrated food initiatives managed by local NGOs, which bring together, for example, the themes of inclusion, community-building, vegetable gardens and waste management; (2) the need to relaunch local agricultural production by providing access to (new) markets (particularly public food procurement) to avoid land abandonment, among others; (3) the need to foster and enlarge participation in the FPN while aiming to achieve concrete results in terms of influencing policy responses and the allocation of a dedicated public budget; (4) the need to facilitate a cultural change and valorise local healthy diets, starting from food education in schools and with families.

Strategic planning: The lines of action that were identified revolve around the restart of the food policy theme in three working groups: (1) food education, (2) local food production and supply chains, and (3) food security/food poverty. The upcoming work in relation to these themes, especially the first two, will be related to one central process, namely the transition towards the **school canteens' management system** of a local company model named "Qualità and Servizi" within the municipality of Capannori. More precisely, this means preparing the way for **local procurement** as well as the construction of a community where different perspectives are represented to ensure the sustainability and quality of the future service.

Facilitators were identified for each working group. These will be in charge of putting together the plan of action, involving participants and developing the real-life interventions (RLIs) in more detail. The theme of food poverty/security was discussed during the visioning events but will also be part of the focus of the RLIs.

In addition, issues were raised internally to the LL in relation to the geographic scope of the strategic plan. While the thematic working groups will in the long run work across the whole area of the Piana di Lucca, the RLIs (and the focus around the transition towards the "Qualità e Servizi" school canteens management model) mainly concern the municipality of Capannori. This municipality owns indeed more material resources to start experimenting in this direction. While playing as frontrunner, it will share reflections and lessons learned with the other public administrations that are part of the FPN along the way.

Table 17: Overview of results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process in Capannori, Lucca

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & PARTNER RESPONSIBILITIES	POTENTIAL INDICATORS FOR SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Local agricultural production and food supply chains	Support local agricultural production by providing access to (new) markets to avoid land abandonment	Support the transition toward a new school canteens' public food procurement model focusing on local production and community building	Facilitation, best practices and knowledge exchange and expert advice to assist the transition towards the new model, possibly supported in parallel in one or more RLI and the corresponding thematic working group (upcoming)	- no. of local producers involved in the preparatory work
Community	Develop integrated projects that can build on healthy food practices to better connect local inhabitants	Better support public policies and public-third sector partnerships for enlarging access to food security programs	Continuous mapping of existing policy and community initiatives and best practices related to food	- no. of inhabitants reached by activities
Participation	Foster and enlarge participation to the FPN while aiming to achieve concrete results in terms of policy response and dedicated public budget	Restart the thematic working groups of the FPN, in particular: food education and school canteens; food security; short food chains and strengthening the relation between local production and public canteen	Re-activated/re-started participatory activities in thematic working groups	- No. of participants attending each working group meeting and/or overall
Education	Enhance a cultural change starting from food education in schools/with families	Organize food education workshops in schools around the protein transition, the prevention of food waste and school meals	Facilitation, training (e.g. regulatory aspects), best practices exchange, and linkages to the rest of the visioning themes, for planning and implementing activities and labs in schools	No. of projects in schools

Lessons learned in Capannori through the visioning & strategic planning process

The integration of the project's aims and methods in the existing local agenda of events was worthwhile, ending up with multiple moments of reflection (and activities, in the school labs' event) with a very diverse audience. All workshops were useful also internally to the Living Lab and the municipality of Capannori to receive feedback from local inhabitants and to avoid replicating some

organizational mistake from the past. At the same time, it was the opportunity to practically feel the importance of dividing more clearly specific responsibilities and tasks internally to the Living Lab. At the time of writing, some key experts on the ground were being identified. These include long-established members of the Piana del Cibo, but also new civil servants internally to the municipality to be engaged in this process as well as task-oriented consultants to work at effectively re-establishing the working groups on the ground.

LISBON

Photo: Rodrigo Pimenta – DNA Cascais

Context for visioning and strategy workshops

In 2019, the Living Lab of the European project ROBUST (Rural-Urban Outlooks: Unlocking Synergies) gave rise to the creation of the first Food Policy Network (FPN) in the Lisbon city-region, which evolved into a formalized network called FoodLink – Network for Food Transition in the Lisbon Metropolitan Area. FoodLink aimed to develop a comprehensive food strategy for the entire region through a participatory process from March 2023 to February 2024 that brought together a broad representation of actors from different sectors and the validation of the different institutions in the area. The FoodCLIC Living Lab Lisbon is fully embedded within this metropolitan strategy, with the Portuguese partners acting as promoters of this process.

The Lisbon Metropolitan Area (LMA) has a complex and interconnected food system that involves the city and the surrounding region. Key challenges include understanding and addressing complex challenges associated with, among others, multi-actor collaboration across the region, an interdisciplinary approach, systemic thinking, policy development, community engagement, innovation, technological integration, and adaptation. The food system is closely related to other urban domains, such as transportation, health, land use planning for agriculture, community development, job creation, and waste management, and its transformation requires the integral participation of stakeholders from different sectors.

Sense-making activities

To effectively implement the FoodCLIC approach, the Lisbon Living Lab decided to focus on the area of Cascais. For the metropolitan strategy, the Living Lab team held internal meetings with the 18 municipal councils of the LMA to promote collaboration among various stakeholders throughout the region. For the definition of a municipal food transition strategy in Cascais, the Living Lab team organized meetings with local partners, such as the local government department (for example, Terras de Cascais, territorial valorisation planning department). They agreed that the project process needed to be dynamized at the local level within the region through a bottom-up and participatory approach, with pilot interventions in two selected vulnerable neighbourhoods within the Council (Adroana and Cabeço de Mouro), where the effectiveness of interventions in the local context can be demonstrated. The agreed strategy starts from the residents' needs and aims to empower them to participate in planning, decision-making, and implementation processes. By recognizing the strengths and unique knowledge of these areas, the approach aimed to promote active participation and support self-development.

Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops – Implementation & Outcomes

Implementation: Both for the *system understanding and visioning workshop* and for the *strategic planning workshop*, three meetings were organised: one focused on the inputs about the food system at the municipal and regional level; the other two focused on inputs from residents of each neighbourhood targeted by the planned interventions: Adroana and Cabeço do Mouro.

WORKSHOP TOPIC	MUNICIPAL AND REGIONAL LEVEL	ADROANA NEIGHBORHOOD	CABECO DO MOURO NEIGH.
System understanding and visioning	30 th October 2023	11 th January 2024	12 th January 2024
Strategic planning	10 th January 2024		

The methodology of the Cascais workshops followed a three-part collaborative process: first, an introductory session explained FoodCLIC’s purposes and timeline which then led into an interactive groupwork session using large scale printed maps of Cascais and the two neighbourhoods Adroana and Cabeço do Mouro. On these maps, participants were free to illustrate and write down ideas of what they would envision for each setting’s food system by the year 2050. At the end, individual contributions to the participatory visioning maps were voted on using dotmocracy – each participant responded to the maps with red and green stickers representing two criteria: whether the action or idea was needed, and whether it was perceived as attainable.

In part two of the workshops, participants were asked to discuss and share ideas to get an understanding of key enablers or disablers to healthy and sustainable food access for all in Cascais, particularly for those living in vulnerable neighbourhoods.

Lastly, the third session aimed to discuss the role some policies and planning frameworks as specific factors in progressing outcomes to healthy, sustainable and inclusive food environments and how these enable or disable the visioning goals.

The local workshops were held in DNA Cascais, an agency for entrepreneurship and innovation managed by the Cascais city council. Stakeholders attending the visioning and the strategic planning workshops had either participated in previous mapping and gapping activities or were identified and invited to balance and expand the representativity of all dimensions of the quadruple helix. In both cases, about 20 stakeholders attended, representing local government departments, public food production initiatives from the Ministry of Justice, research and education organisations, business and food entrepreneurs from the production, manufacturing and distribution sectors, and civil society organisations.

An artist created three drawings depicting the transformation of the food system in the Municipality of Cascais. These drawings were presented during the strategic planning workshop, which followed the visioning workshop that generated ideas for the food system's vision in 2050 at both the municipality and neighbourhood levels.

Figure 9 Illustrations based on the inputs of visioning workshop participants, carried forward to stimulate strategic action planning; Artist: Nathalia Bagatini

The neighbourhood workshops were organised as joint dinners and combined the system understanding and visioning with strategic planning. Sessions took place in social housing estates, gathering residents’ views on the priorities at the neighbourhood level. These were preceded by conversations about the preconceived objectives before the meeting. The dinner in Adroana was held in the neighbourhood’s Ludoteca, with 16 local residents in attendance. The dinner in Cabeço de Moura was held in the neighbourhood’s Ecoludoteca, with 10 local residents attending.

The format of these meetings was more informal to enable residents to contribute openly and were accompanied by a shared meal cooked by a resident of the neighbourhood and facilitated by Cascais Ambiente. During these sessions with stakeholders from diverse professional backgrounds and experiences, moderators and co-moderators were on hand to promote opportunities for all participants to share and listen to others’ contributions and experiences, registering discordances between perspectives when applicable.

For the follow-up strategic planning workshops, the format both at the municipality and neighbourhood level was divided into four sessions, each consisting of a content presentation, plenary discussion, and the use of Mentimeter for voting and Q&A. These workshops aimed to balance time dedicated to targeted discussion, feedback and validation in order to guide dialog and build decision-making consensus on key topics: the primary guidelines for a food transition strategy in Cascais, the actions prioritized for implementation in neighbourhoods with the most vulnerable populations, the identifiable governance options that would enable the food strategy implementations, and the areas of knowledge and skills to be strengthened in order to empower local implementation partners.

Table 98: Participating organizations in the Visioning and Strategic Planning Workshops in Lisbon

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Workshops at the municipal and regional level			
Indústria e Comercio Alimentar, S.A. Cascais Center (ICA) (Food entrepreneurs)	Business/industry (2)	Vitamimos (Food entrepreneurs working with "food-deprived and vulnerable" groups)	Business/industry
Food4Sustainability (NGO)	Civil Society	Biofrade (Local food distributors)	Business/industry
Local Approach (NGO)	Civil Society	Trato Lixo (Collection and treatment of urban waste)	Business/industry
Fundação Champagnat (Social aid)	Civil Society (2)	Indústria e Comercio Alimentar, S.A. Cascais Center (ICA) (Food entrepreneurs)	Business/industry (2)
Associação Portuguesa Contra a Obesidade Infantil (APCOI) (Food aid organisation)	Civil Society	APPC - Associação de profissionais da pesca de Cascais (Food producers)	Business/industry
Câmara municipal de Cascais – FoodLab (Food social aid)	Local Government	Câmara municipal de Cascais - Departamento de Coesão e Desenvolvimento Social (DDS), Divisão de Recursos para a inclusão social (Social Inclusion Resources Division)	Local Government
Cascais Ambiente - Divisão Terras de Cascais - Iniciativas públicas de produção alimentar (Public municipality food production initiative)	Local Government (4)	Cascais Ambiente - Divisão Terras de Cascais - Iniciativas públicas de produção alimentar (Public municipality food production initiative)	Local Government (4)
Câmara municipal de Cascais - Departamento de Educação Divisão de Administração e Gestão Educativa (Educational Administration and Management Division)	Local Government	Agrupamento de Centros de Saúde (ACES) Cascais (Health institution)	Local Government

VISIONING WORKSHOP		STRATEGIC PLANNING WORKSHOP	
Organization	Sector	Organization	Sector
Estabelecimento Prisional de Tires - Iniciativas públicas de produção alimentar (Public municipality food production initiative)	Local Government	Câmara municipal de Cascais - Departamento Local de Saúde e Solidariedade Social (Local health and social solidarity servisse)	Local Government
Estabelecimento Prisional de Linhó - Iniciativas públicas de produção alimentar (Public municipality food production initiative)	Local Government	Câmara municipal de Cascais - Departamento de Educação (DED) Divisão de Administração e Gestão Educativa (Educational Administration and Management Division) - Unidade qualidade da segurança alimentar (Food safety quality unit)	Local Government (2)
Câmara municipal de Cascais - Departamento Local de Saúde e Solidariedade Social (Local health and social solidarity servisse)	Local Government (4)	Câmara Municipal de Cascais - Departamento de Educação (DED) Divisão de Administração e Gestão Educativa (Educational Administration and Management Division)	Local Government
Câmara municipal de Cascais - Departamento de Coesão e Desenvolvimento Social (DDS), Divisão de Recursos para a inclusão social (Social Inclusion Resources Division)	Local Government	ULisboa – Faculdade de Medicina Lisboa (FMUL) (Faculty of Medicine)	Research/Education
Escola Superior de Hotelaria e Turismo do Estoril (ESHTE) (Estoril School of Hospitality and Tourism)	Research/Education	Faculdade de Ciências Sociais e Humanas (FCSH) Universidade NOVA de Lisboa (Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities NOVA University Lisbon)	Research/Education
		Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia FCT – Nova - Projeto CitySelf (Faculty of Science and Technology)	Research/Education
		Food4Sustainability (NGO)	Civil Society
		Associação Portuguesa Contra a Obesidade Infantil (APCOI) / Héris da fruta (Food aid organisation)	Civil Society
Combined Visioning and Strategic planning workshops (held in neighbourhoods)			
Adroana neighbourhood (social houses)	Civil Society (16)		
Cabeço de Mouro neighbourhood (social houses)	Civil Society (9)		

Key understandings of food systems problems: Visioning is a demanding task for those who are not familiar with the planning methodologies because it implies projecting over time a mixture of

reality with ideas about desirable futures in an integrated and coherent formulation. The first version of the vision for the municipality did not seem to be particularly ambitious, and it was perceived as a bit vague. On the other hand, the visions defined for the neighbourhoods were diverse in the sense that they included various dimensions. At the same time, they were also dispersed and not sufficiently consistent.

After discussing this preliminary version within the context of the vision established for the region, new contributions were collected, and a more complete and integrated vision was developed. Although there is no formally established FPN in Cascais, there exists a group of local entities that regularly convene to discuss and make decisions together. This may explain why the participants were able to follow most of the workshop discussions, even though they attended intermittently. This can be interpreted as an indication that there are good conditions for setting up an FPN in the near future.

Vision for Lisbon's future food system: Following a comprehensive discussion of various scenarios, a consensus was reached, and the original vision for the metropolitan food system was updated as follows:

By 2030, at least 15 per cent of the food supply for the population living in the metropolitan area should be provided locally, based on:

- sustainable production methods, including organic production, integrated production/protection and agroecology;
- innovative solutions, particularly in the field of water management for irrigation, the reduction of phytopharmaceuticals, soil conservation and nutrient balance, and climate adaptation, energy efficiency and alternative energies;
- low carbon distribution networks and local food circuits that fulfil the criteria of inclusion and food safety;
- a brand that identifies and differentiates the products and agents of the food system that are associated with the implementation of the ETA-AML;
- certified products that will be available and accessible for healthy and sustainable food consumption, essential for the health and well-being of all citizens;
- the reduction of food waste in all sectors of the food system;
- the treatment and valorisation of organic food waste in a logic of circularity;
- offering training programmes for the food transition to all actors in the food system;
- increasing food literacy, investing primarily in the school-age population;
- the creation of opportunities for recreation and gastronomic and cultural tourism in the metropolitan area, as an innovative initiative that contributes to regional socio-ecological and economic development and the strengthening of urban-rural synergies;
- increasing institutional culture to strengthen synergies at intersectoral level and plurality in the participatory dimension between the various levels of action.

Strategic planning: The identified themes included all the different steps of the food system process (food production through consumption) and related to all of the different food environments. They were discussed and voted upon by the stakeholders, taking into consideration the diversity of each other's backgrounds. Four lines of action were prioritised:

1. Food literacy promotion: focused on empowering citizens from a "farm to fork" perspective to achieve a healthy and sustainable diet adapted to the context in which they live: food production, processing, access and consumption of food and related skills;
2. Provision of land with agricultural potential for the creation of business models that should integrate technological innovation;
3. Valorisation of resources (e.g. soil and water) in food production: including rain harvesting and exploitation of all land with agricultural potential (for sustainable agriculture);
4. Valorisation of food waste: through the reduction of food waste and organic waste composting system.

During the sessions with the neighbourhoods' residents, prioritised lines of action adapted to the neighbourhood-specific context were also identified. In Adroana, aligned with the other stakeholders' perspectives, the residents prioritised the promotion of food literacy. Improved access to food retail spaces (through the increase in public transportation frequency and lines) and other parallel themes, such as the promotion of physical activity and psychological support, were also stressed. In Cabeço do Mouro, residents prioritised community food production through the setting up of a community urban garden. It was proposed that this initiative could also respond to other prioritised topics, such as children's safety, through the integrated implementation of a play space for children in the community urban gardens.

Table19: Overview of the results from the Visioning & Strategic Planning process in Lisbon

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
Food literacy promotion	Increase citizen food-related competencies and knowledge	Develop and implement a long-term food education program with a "farm to fork" perspective	Social society local associations Food education specialists Citizens Schools	- Survey
Food production business models	Facilitate the establishment of local food production businesses	Food education specialists	Local government partners and technicians – Terras de Cascais	- No. of local food production businesses - No. of food produced
Valorisation of resources in food production	Optimise the usage of water and land for local food production	Introduce in urban community gardens new technologies	Local government partners and technicians	- No. of new resource-saving installations

THEME(S)	OBJECTIVE(S)	ACTIONS	REQUIRED RESOURCES & RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	POTENTIAL INDICATORS AS SIGNS OF SUCCESS
		such as rain harvest		
Valorisation of food waste	Improve circular systems through alternative purposes for food waste	Create pilot programmes where community gardens use compost from domestic food waste valorisation	Local government partners and technicians – Terras de Cascais Enterprise responsible for the urban collection and management of solid waste	- No. of new initiatives to reduce food waste
Community food production	Increase alternative methods to access fresh produce	Implement a community garden	Local government partners and technicians Citizens	- No. of new initiatives to access fresh produces - Estimated no. of people reached

Lessons learned in Lisbon through the visioning & strategic planning process

The events proceeded as planned without any significant alterations. However, it is noteworthy that the discussion became more stimulating and innovative once it moved beyond the pre-defined templates. While following a structured methodology was useful initially, it would have been beneficial to allocate some time and space for a more spontaneous and open-ended discussion, when the discussion evolves into something beyond the templates.

The success of the entire process depends on the use of diverse techniques and complementary approaches to allow people to interact and experience various formats. Hosting discussions in a plenary mode has proven to be productive, as it allows everyone to listen and participate in the debate simultaneously. Additionally, working groups provide a platform for deeper discussions and the generation of ideas.

Engaging a broader range of stakeholders would lead to a more comprehensive and fruitful discussion. It would be beneficial to compare the position of the Cascais municipality, which has a high number of representatives, with the positions of other stakeholders involved in the local food system. As the co-design process progresses, it is essential to provide relevant information not only from previous sessions but also official data to help participants get prepared for upcoming sessions.

PARTNERS

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